

List of Fishes of the Galapagos Archipelago, Ecuador (Version 3.0)

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Introduction

In preparation for the revised new edition of the 1997 book “The Fishes of the Galapagos Islands” by Jack Stein Grove and Robert J. Lavenberg, to be published by the EPCA, the East Pacific Corridor Alliance Foundation (www.epcafoundation.org), we have been reviewing literature and museum records and obtaining additional underwater photographs and specimens of fishes from Galapagos waters. Our Version 2.0 of the species list in Victor et al. (2024) added a number of cryptobenthic species, new records, and unresolved taxa, many documented from the expedition sponsored by the EPCA in May 2024, which included widespread surveys, intensive underwater photography, and collecting of tissues for DNA sequencing.

We update the fish species list here, adding mostly deeper or mesopelagic species, but also clarifying and correcting a number of species in the prior lists, applying strict scientific criteria (Grove et al. 2022, Victor et al. 2024). The addition of deeper and mesopelagic species is based on a detailed review of collections at the Scripps Institution of Oceanography’s Marine Vertebrate Collection (SIO), where collections from the extensive EASTROPAC offshore oceanic trawl surveys are housed and where original collection notes are preserved, many available online (at <https://sioapps.ucsd.edu/collections/mv/>). The large-scale EASTROPAC I and II surveys were conducted in the 1950s and 1960s for the National Marine Fisheries Service, extending deep into the TEP region. In those surveys, multiple ships sampled along 3000-km transects from Baja California to south of the equator. A series of expeditions by SIO also surveyed offshore and deep fishes in the region: the Shellback expedition in 1952; the R/V *Alpha Helix* with Richard Rosenblatt in the 1960s; and the Krill expedition to the Galapagos Rise in the 1970s. There have been a few more recent CalCOFI larval surveys that extend to Galapagos waters, with results listed at GBIF, however, larval observation records, in our protocol, are not included. The collections at SIO, and to a lesser degree at LACM and CAS (with the R/V *Arcturus* 1925 collection), account for almost all of the accessible offshore collections of fishes in the TEP region.

There are also collections from a number of Russian ichthyological surveys in the area, but they are not accessible and only a few of the results are documented in the English literature. Other collections are much smaller and often not collated in any detail, and, since the identification of offshore deeper and mesopelagic species is particularly difficult, most do not provide reliable species identifications. The SIO collections were collated and identified by experts in the taxonomy of deeper and mesopelagic fishes of the eastern Pacific, in particular by Carl Hubbs, Richard Rosenblatt, Robert Wisner, Basil Nafpaktitis, and Al Ebeling, who over the years annotated the data with identifications, numbers, and size ranges of fishes collected. Note that some of those specimens listed are larval and those species records were not considered for inclusion in the Galapagos fish species list, conforming with most other range compilations, e.g. The American Fisheries Society list of common and scientific names (Page et al. 2023). The exclusion is discussed in Version 2.0 of Victor et al. (2024): in brief, vast numbers of larvae of continental shorefishes, including brackish and even freshwater species, can be advected far offshore and into the Galapagos EEZ (Victor 2024), where they do not survive or persist. Including them in faunal lists would grossly expand the list making it much less meaningful or useful, and, if only theoretically, larval records would progressively expand the list to eventually include all of the known fishes from the entire southeastern Pacific Ocean.

Results

The total number of species in this version of the list is augmented by 36 to 719 total species (from 683), whilst the number of families stays the same. The updated list of fishes known to occur on and around the Archipelago are listed in **taxonomic** order in Table 1 and in **family alphabetical** order in Table 2, with added species and corrections in bold font (in all tables).

The area covered is defined as that encompassed by the Ecuadorean EEZ limits around the Galapagos Archipelago, which extend well beyond the boundaries of the Galapagos Marine Reserve (Reserva Marina de Galápagos) and also include the new Reserva Marina Hermandad (in the waters between Galapagos and the outer border of the Costa Rican EEZ limits surrounding Cocos Island). The area covered includes the islands and adjoining shelf slope down to and including the abyssal region and seamounts.

The 719 listed species of fishes include 60 in Chondrichthyes (in 28 families) and 650 bony fishes (Osteichthyes, in 151 families), plus 8 hagfishes (Myxiniformes) and one cephalochordate. The 38 additions (there were two removals to net 36) comprise 5 shallow shorefishes, 24 mesopelagic species, 5 deepwater (non-pelagic) species, and 4 offshore pelagic species. One offshore pelagic species is removed (and two species are moved from nearshore pelagic to offshore pelagic); and one shallow shorefish species is removed (another is replaced with a newly described endemic species). Two previously listed endemics are corrected to non-endemic, two non-endemics are corrected to endemic, and 5 vagrants are changed to resident. A number of spellings are corrected.

There are 69 documented **endemic** species in 31 families (including 7 chondrichthyan species in 4 families and 8 myxinids), about half deeper-water demersal species (32 endemics in 14 families) and the remainder mostly shallow reef species with relatively short larval lives, such as blennioids, dactyloscopids, gobioids, and haemulids (37 shallow endemics in 19 families) (Table 3). As expected, there are no endemic mesopelagic or inshore pelagic or offshore pelagic species (and no endemic vagrants by definition).

Updated estimates of percent endemism for the Galapagos fish fauna are presented in Table A. The most useful percentages are **9.6%** for all fishes, but that is not a stable estimate. More consistent is **10.7%** for residents (excluding vagrants, which are not part of the “fauna” and inevitably are ever-accumulating numbers). Then a more island-oriented estimate is **13.6%** for residents excluding the large set of mesopelagic fishes that can mount in numbers and become a source of distortion.

TABLE A
Percentage endemism for a variety of fish faunal categories in the Galapagos Islands

(NUM is total count of species; END is the number of endemics in that category; %= % endemism
note mesopelagic and offshore pelagic fishes have no endemics)

Category	code	ALL CLASSES*			Osteichthyes			Chondrichthyes			Chondrichthyes + Myxini		
		NUM	END	%	NUM	END	%	NUM	END	%	NUM	END	%
all fishes	all	719	69	9.6	650	54	8.3	60	7	11.7	68	15	22.1
all resident fishes	all-v	642	69	10.7	576	54	9.4	57	7	12.3	65	15	23.1
all fishes without mesopelagics	all-meso	583	69	11.8	515	54	10.5	59	7	11.9	67	15	22.4
all resident fishes without mesopelagics	all-meso-v	506	69	13.6	441	54	12.2	56	7	12.5	64	15	23.4
shorefishes (shallow & nearshore & deep)	ss+nsp+ds	482	69	14.3	443	54	12.2	30	7	23.3	38	15	39.5
resident shorefishes (shallow ns & deep)	ss+nsp+ds-v	411	69	16.8	372	54	14.5	30	7	23.3	38	15	39.5
all inshore fishes without nearshore	ss+ds	456	69	15.1	417	54	12.9	30	7	23.3	38	15	39.5
resident inshore fishes without nearshore	ss+ds-v	390	69	17.7	351	54	15.4	30	7	23.3	38	15	39.5
all shallow fishes including inshore & offshore pelagic	ss+nsp+op	457	37	8.1	420	37	8.8	36	0	0	36	0	0
resident shallow fishes including inshore & offshore pelagic	ss+nsp+op-v	382	37	9.7	348	37	10.6	33	0	0	33	0	0
shallow shorefishes inshore & nearshore **	ss+nsp	356	37	10.4	348	37	10.6	7	0	0	7	0	0
resident shallow shorefishes in & near	ss+nsp-v	287	37	12.9	279	37	13.3	7	0	0	7	0	0
shallow inshore fishes	ss	330	37	11.2	322	37	11.5	7	0	0	7	0	0
resident shallow inshore fishes	ss-v	266	37	13.9	258	37	14.3	7	0	0	7	0	0
deep inshore fishes	ds	126	32	25.4	95	17	17.9	23	7	30.4	31	15	48.4
resident deep inshore fishes	ds-v	124	32	25.8	93	17	18.3	23	7	30.4	31	15	48.4

* includes the one cephalochordate

a commonly used category used by many **diving guidebooks for shorefish observed in usual diving depths (shallow shorefishes plus nearshore pelagics, including vagrants).

Of the total, 77 species are considered **vagrants** (3 chondrichthyans), many of which are Indo-Pacific coral-reef species that are transported across the east Pacific barrier as a rare individual (Table 4). That leaves a total of 642 resident species (57 chondrichthyans). How we assign vagrant is covered in detail in Victor et al. (2024), but basically only rare isolated records of one or two individuals are considered vagrant, clearly precluding a self-sustaining local population, while observations or collections of repeated or multiple individuals together moves a fish into resident category. Notably, species that are well-hidden, small and cryptic, or difficult to find or survey, including most sporadic deeper-water species we do not survey effectively, are considered resident even with rare or single records, until proven otherwise.

For broad habitat categories, we define **shorefishes** broadly, as non-pelagic species, including those small schooling fishes off the bottom but associated with the shoreline and we also include bottom-associated deeper and slope and even abyssal species, mainly because there is no sharp demarcation between deep-slope fauna to abyssal fishes. We do separate out the large set of carangid fishes which move inshore and offshore but are broadly associated with coastal waters as shallow **nearshore pelagics**.

Fishes that are found mainly out in open ocean are **offshore pelagics**, but if they are the large group of mostly small, vertically migrating fish families, they are categorized as **mesopelagic**. One elasmobranch, the bigeye thresher shark *Alopias superciliosus*, spends daylight hours in the mesopelagic zone and at night ascends to feed, in parallel with other mesopelagic fishes.

The line between **shallow** and **deep** is not easily defined, but we consider fishes that could be seen by regular divers as shallow, generally up to 50 m deep.

For the Galapagos, there are 330 shorefishes in shallow waters: made up of 266 shallow residents (in 79 families) (Table 5) and 64 shallow vagrants (in 34 families, 7 of which occur in Galapagos only as vagrants). In addition, there are 13 deepwater (2) or pelagic vagrants (nearshore 5 and offshore 6). There are also 26 resident nearshore pelagics (Carangidae, with 5 vagrants) (Table 5); 126 deepwater bottom fishes (Table 6) (in 46 families, only two vagrants); 101 offshore pelagics (in 38 families; 6 vagrants) (Table 7); and 136 mesopelagic species (in 30 families) (Table 8).

Notes on changes to the Version 2.0 list

Additions

Acanthurus leucocheilus (Acanthuridae) is added as a vagrant shallow shorefish based on a single photograph of two large adults at Wolf Island by WBS in 2024 (iNat) (Bensted-Smith et al. 2025). No other report of this prominent and easily identified widespread Indo-Pacific surgeonfish exists for the TEP.

Acanthurus olivaceus (Acanthuridae) is added as a vagrant shallow shorefish based on a single photograph of one adult at Marchena by WBS in 2024 (iNat) (Bensted-Smith et al. 2025). No other report of this prominent and easily identified widespread Indo-Pacific surgeonfish exists for the TEP.

Ctenochaetus marginatus (Acanthuridae) is added based on numerous sightings and photographs in Galapagos in 2024 (iNat) (Bensted-Smith et al. 2025). It is surprising that this Indo-Pacific surgeonfish had not been previously documented in the Archipelago since it is widely reported from the TEP, at Islas Revillagigedo, Clipperton, Cocos Island, and Malpelo, as well as along the mainland at Mexico, Costa Rica, Panama, and Colombia (Robertson & Allen 2024). Galapagos observations have been on the northern islands of Darwin and Wolf, most by author WBS, where Indo-Pacific arrivals are concentrated, but C. Estapé and A. Morgan-Estapé also photographed a small adult at Pinta Island, in Fig. 2C of Bensted-Smith et al. (2025). Given the number of sightings and frequent pairs, the species is considered a resident shallow shorefish. At Clipperton they can be abundant (Robertson & Allen 1997), 71 juveniles were collected on the 1998 expedition by STRI (BV collection).

Bathylagus wesethi (Bathylagidae) is added as based on SIO 91-164, as a mesopelagic species.

Brama japonica (Bramidae) is added as a vagrant offshore pelagic species based on SIO 64-222, a juvenile 161 mm SL specimen from the stomach of a bigeye tuna caught in fisheries at Cadillac Bank. The species is a well-studied temperate north Pacific fish with the southern limit in the eastern Pacific cited in literature as off mid-

Baja California; other than the tuna-stomach specimen, another juvenile is reported from tropical waters, from a yellowfin tuna set (at 9°N, 121°W; SIO 84-63); other than the two juveniles, only a couple of larvae have been collected. In contrast, *Brama dussumieri* is a tropical species found circumglobally in tropical waters and widespread in the TEP; it is on the list based on SIO 92-72 & 63-1023 within the EEZ.

Thermichthys hollisi (Bythitidae) is added as a deepwater non-pelagic endemic species based on the holotype SIO 88-97 described by Cohen, Rosenblatt & Moser (1990) from the Galapagos Rift hydrothermal vents, reviewed by Chen et al. (2024). Nielsen & Cohen (2002) note how divergent this species is from other *Thermichthys* species and propose *Gerhadia* as a new genus for this species, however it remains *Thermichthys* in Fricke et al. (2026).

Chaetodon punctatofasciatus (Chaetodontidae) is added as a vagrant shallow shorefish based on a single photograph of a pair of adults at Pinta Island by F. Terán in 2024 (Bensted-Smith et al. 2025). This widespread Indo-Pacific butterflyfish has not been reported elsewhere in the TEP.

Epinephelus quinquefasciatus (Epinephelidae) is added as a vagrant shallow shorefish based on an underwater video from Isla San Cristobal, taken by Jose Martinez, passed on by the Parque Nacional Galápagos to WBS for identification. The video shows a massive grouper, apparently more than 1.5 meters long, with an overall uniform dark-mottled body without bars, a flattened long forehead, a small eye, relatively short dorsal-fin spines, and a smooth-edged, rounded-off, paddle-like caudal fin with distal round dark spots and no white margin.

Cheilopogon furcatus (Exocoetidae) is added based on SIO 12-1263, which was collected along with a *C. dorsomacula* in that collection. *Cheilopogon dorsomacula* was considered a subspecies of *C. furcatus* until elevated, thus older TEP records of *C. furcatus* may represent *C. dorsomacula*. The two species are distinguished by the presence of black markings on the pelvic and dorsal fins in *C. dorsomacula* vs. unpigmented on *C. furcatus*. These flyingfishes are offshore pelagic species.

Cyclothone braueri (Gonostomatidae) is added based on 140 specimens in SIO 05-154, as a mesopelagic species.

Cyclothone microdon (Gonostomatidae) is added as a mesopelagic species based on SIO 55-258, with 18 specimens from 33–56 mm SL; 5 species of *Cyclothone* were identified in the collection including 460 specimens of *C. acclinidens*.

Cyclothone pseudopallida (Gonostomatidae) is added as a mesopelagic species based on SIO 55-258; a single 38 mm SL specimen was listed; 5 species of *Cyclothone* were identified in the collection including 460 specimens of *C. acclinidens*.

Sigmops elongatus (Gonostomatidae) is added based on SIO 76-55, as a mesopelagic species (ex-*Gonostoma elongatum*).

Nezumia parini (Macrouridae) is added as a deepwater non-pelagic endemic species based on a record in Parin et al. (1990) from 0°, -89°.

Centrobranchus andreae (Myctophidae) is added based on SIO 76-59, as a mesopelagic species.

Dasyscopelus asper (Myctophidae) is added based on SIO 84-199, as a mesopelagic species (ex-*Myctophum asperum*).

Diaphus fulgens (Myctophidae) is added based on SIO 91-161 etc., as a mesopelagic species.

Diaphus mollis (Myctophidae) is added based on SIO 91-165 etc., as a mesopelagic species.

Diaphus parri (Myctophidae) is added based on SIO 91-163 etc., as a mesopelagic species.

Lampanyctus crypticus (Myctophidae) is added based on SIO 96-151 etc., as a mesopelagic species.

Lampanyctus nobilis (Myctophidae) is added based on SIO 72-38, as a mesopelagic species.

Protomyctophum sp. (Myctophidae) is added based on SIO 05-154, as a mesopelagic species; there are at least 12 species that are reported as circumglobal, southern circumglobal, or present in the eastern Pacific.

Triphoturus nigricans (Myctophidae) is added based on SIO 95-63 etc., as a mesopelagic species.

Avocettina infans (Nemichthyidae) is added based on SIO 76-59, as a mesopelagic species. An additional record of *Avocettina* sp. is reported by Parin et al. (1990) from 0°, -89°.

Cubiceps baxteri (Nomeidae) is added based on specimens from SIO 75-84, as an offshore pelagic species. *Cubiceps caeruleus*, *C. paradoxus*, and *C. capensis* are widespread but not yet recorded within the Galapagos EEZ.

Scopelosaurus harryi (Notosudidae) is added based on a specimen from SIO 95-62, as a mesopelagic species. Virtually all specimens are from temperate latitudes, but a few are recorded within the tropics.

Porogadus promelas (Ophidiidae) is added based on the report from Cohen & Haedrich (1983) of a specimen of *Porogadus* sp. found moribund at the surface over the vent site (SIO 72-108), the species is added as a deepwater non-pelagic species. This ophidiid fish was not included in the recent update of hydrothermal-vent fauna by Chen et al. (2024), who reported only three fishes (a bythitid and two zoarcids). Schwartzhans & Møller (2021) reviewed the genus and conclude there are three *Porogadus* species in the TEP (but they did not examine SIO 72-108 or mention Galapagos), i.e. *P. atripectus* from Baja California to Ecuador, *P. longiceps* from the Panama Bight, and the very widespread *P. promelas* ranging from British Columbia to Chile. A larva collected over the Rose Garden hydrothermal vents (Victor 2024) has an almost identical COI mtDNA sequence (BOLD BIN AAF8119) to a known *P. promelas* from British Columbia (sequenced specimens included in Schwartzhans & Møller as RBCM 010-00342-001) and to the “*Porogadus* sp.” collected off Panama in the MOP survey (Robertson et al. 2017; p. 63, USNM 421448, 421549 & 435796; not examined by Schwartzhans & Møller). The MOP specimens furthermore have the relatively short snout characteristic of *P. promelas* (the TEP sister species of Atlantic *P. catena*). Thus the *Porogadus* sp. collected over the vents is presumed to represent *P. promelas*.

Spectrunculus crassus (Ophidiidae) is added based on records of “*Parabassogigas*” from Galapagos (including USNM 217828 & 217829 from the R/V *Anton Bruun* expedition in 1966), as a deepwater non-pelagic species.. Cohen & Haedrich (1983) documented abyssal vent-associated fishes at the Galapagos hydrothermal vents and they list *Spectrunculus* (without species) as “common”. *Parabassogigas* has since been synonymized with *Spectrunculus* and the erstwhile monotypic species *S. grandis* has been split into 4 species, with *S. crassus* the representative in the TEP (Uiblein et al. 2023; the review did not include any specimens from the Galapagos). *Bassogigas coheni* Mayer & Nalbant, 1972, described from Peru, is considered a junior synonym of *S. crassus*.

Bathylchnops sp. (Opisthoproctidae) is added as a mesopelagic species based on an 11-mm specimen from SIO 05-154. There are three known species, any of which could be in the TEP: circumglobal *Bathylchnops brachyrhynchus* (Parr, 1937); *B. chilensis* Parin, Belyanina & Evseenko, 2009 from the SE Pacific; and *B. exilis* Cohen, 1958 from the north Pacific and Chile.

Lestidium bigelowi (Paralepididae) is added based on SIO 95-62, as a mesopelagic species.

Vinciguerrria nimbaria (Phosichthyidae) is added based on SIO 52-409 etc., as a mesopelagic species.

Sagamichthys abei Parr, 1953 (Platytroutidae) is added based on SIO 52-409, as a mesopelagic species.

Scomberesox scombroides (Scomberesocidae) is added as an offshore pelagic species based on ranges reported in Hubbs & Wisner (1980), referring to Parin and Ahlstrom collection points that extend into the EEZ, at the periphery of the broad range of the species offshore of Ecuador and Peru (in their Figs. 15 & 17). Originally considered the southern subspecies of *Scomberesox saurus*, it has been elevated to species status, including all southern hemisphere populations. They add that the other resident scomberesocid, *Cololabis adoceta*, can be extremely abundant in the area and that Parin reports a trawl sample just south of Galapagos where a thousand specimens were captured in 20 minutes.

Danaphos oculatus (Sternoptychidae) is added based on SIO 91-197, as a mesopelagic species.

Photonectes margarita (Stomiidae) is added based on SIO 96-149, as a mesopelagic species.

Stomias danae (Stomiidae) is added based on SIO 91-164, as a mesopelagic species.

Thysanactis dentex (Stomiidae) is added based on USNM 298153 (from the R/V *Anton Bruun* in 1966), as a mesopelagic species.

Pachycara rimae (Zoarcidae) is added as a deepwater non-pelagic endemic species based on the holotype LACM 44699-1, described by Anderson (1989) and collected at 2,500 m in 1977 from the Galapagos Rift hydrothermal vents. Chen et al. (2024) reviewed the three fish records from along the rift vents underlying the EEZ line and extending into the EEZ.

Subtractions (note Table B at end of references lists species removed or not accepted for the list in all Versions)

Diodon eydouxi (Diodontidae) is removed from the lists: it is a pelagic pufferfish species found worldwide in warmer waters, however it is infrequently collected and thus far documented specimen records from the TEP are all well north of Galapagos, many within the Intertropical Convergence Zone. The species is on lists for Malpelo Island (Bessudo & LeFevre 2017) and Cocos Island (Cortés 2012; Appendix 1 & Fourriere et al. 2017; Table S2), but, tracking the Cocos citations, the records were attributed to 2008 and 2015 versions of the SFTEP guide by Robertson & Allen (2024). Those listings were derived from the circumtropical range, not any specific reports or specimens. The FAO catalogue for the eastern Pacific does not include any members of the family, without explanation (Fischer et al. 1995). Grove & Lavenberg (1997) label a photograph in Fig. 139 as *D. eydouxi*, but it is a *Chilomycterus reticulatus*, with a rare color pattern with dark fins prominently edged in white.

Carapus mourlani (Ophidiidae: Carapinae) is removed from the lists: the widespread Indo-Pacific species (type location is Madagascar) was included in the Galapagos fauna, based on SIO 04-163 (and listed as Galapagos in VertNet). However, the original collection note has no coordinates, but text saying from Galapagos and as a gift from Eric Parmentier, from the sea cucumber *Isostichopus fuscus* in 2001. Notably, Parmentier et al.'s (2006) discovery of the species was from mainland Ecuador, and were the first confirmed records of the species from the TEP. Parmentier et al. (2006) state that particular specimen is from Punta Ayangué, mainland Ecuador, and it is actually their voucher specimen (confirmed by Eric Parmentier, pers. comm). Subsequently, Glynn et al. (2008) discovered the species in Panama and then Chacon-Monge et al. (2021) found them in Costa Rica. Two earlier putative records, SIO 70-77 from Sonora in 1970 and SIO 11-338 from 1993 at Clarion, Revillagigedo are not mentioned in those articles, and how the difficult species-level identification was made is not documented. The fourth pearlfish species in the TEP, *Carapus dubius*, is reported from the Sea of Cortez to Ecuador, including Cocos Island (and Hawaii) and prefer mollusc hosts. It was described as *Fierasfer dubius* Putnam, 1874 from pearl oysters in the Bay of Panama, and there are no records from Galapagos. Thus far, Grove & Lavenberg (1997) and Robertson & Allen (2024) list neither of the two species; Allen & Robertson (1994) and McCosker & Rosenblatt (2010) list only *C. dubius*, without provenance.

Replacements

Prionotus stephanophrys (Triglidae) is removed from the list and replaced by the newly described endemic Galapagos species *Prionotus pictus* Victor, 2025 (a non-endemic replaced by an endemic). Upon review, *P. stephanophrys* is a continental soft-bottom species not found on the offshore islands of the TEP. Interestingly, almost all underwater photographs labeled as the endemic Galapagos searobin *Prionotus miles*, collected by Charles Darwin and described by Jenyns, are actually of the new species *P. pictus*, which is a colorful reef-associated searobin. True *P. miles* is an uncommon soft-bottom searobin, rarely observed or photographed underwater, but accounting for most museum specimens, likely because it is more easily collected on open substrates and by hook-and-line (Victor 2025). Both of the searobins found in Galapagos are endemic.

Halichoeres melanotis (Labridae) as a vagrant is removed from the list and replaced by *Halichoeres malpelo*, as a resident, based on a set of recent photographs from Darwin, Seymour, and Fernandina by WBS (Bensted-Smith et al. 2025). He documented many individuals, clearly males and females, showing a variety of color patterns consistent with the *Halichoeres melanotis* species complex. The complex includes species with an especially wide range of color patterns, and presently there is a representative on all offshore islands (except Clipperton), as well as the widespread mainland species from the Sea of Cortez to Ecuador. The species native to the Revillagigedo Archipelago was recently described as *Halichoeres sanchezi* Victor, Frable & Ludt, 2024. In that description, the 4 members of the complex are compared in detail with numerous underwater photographs, and the mtDNA-barcode sequence (COI) was obtained for three (except *H. malpelo*). Mainland *H. melanotis* display an extreme range of color patterns in both juveniles and IP and TP adults, notably with a somewhat frequent, distinctive, gold-striped juvenile form. The island species, i.e. *H. sanchezi* in Revillagigedo, *Halichoeres salmofasciatus* in Cocos, and *H. malpelo* in Malpelo, also show a wide variety of

adult color patterns within species, many overlapping, with subtle differences between species. The pair of *H. salmofasciatus* and *H. malpelo* are most similar, and colors are not completely documented, however recently available photographs by authors IK and WBS show that the two species mostly share juvenile and IP color patterns, with reddish lateral stripes and dark spots at the opercular flap and near the base of the caudal fin. One potential difference is raised in the species description of *H. malpelo* (Allen & Robertson 1992), documenting a large IP fish with a pinkish body and yellowish head, recently reinforced by an additional photograph from Malpelo (Bensted-Smith et al. 2025, Fig. 26C). That color form has not been seen at Cocos Island so far, including in recent photographs by IK and BBS (Allen & Robertson 2002). Since a photograph of a large IP in Galapagos (Bensted-Smith et al. 2025, Fig. 24D), shows a somewhat pinkish body and yellowish head, we favor assigning the Galapagos population to *H. malpelo*, pending additional documentation and the collection of specimens for DNA sequencing. Complicating the matter is the original single photograph by Paul Humann from Galapagos decades ago (Humann & DeLoach 2003, p. 105), which more closely resembles color patterns found in mainland populations. That accounted for our listing of vagrant *H. melanotis* in prior versions of the list. However, that unusual appearance may be just another variant within a single Galapagos entity. Genetic analyses of the Galapagos entity are needed, since there are divergences in the mtDNA COI sequence among three species we sequenced, i.e. 2.4% between *H. sanchezi* and *H. melanotis*, 2.9% between *H. sanchezi* and *H. salmofasciatus*, and 2.1% between *H. melanotis* and *H. salmofasciatus*, while *H. malpelo* and *H. salmofasciatus* share a mtDNA lineage (José Tavera, pers. comm.). The barcode sequence of the Galapagos population should help narrow down the identification and may well suggest it represents a new endemic species.

Corrections

Bathytroctes macrolepis (Alepocephalidae) was added in Version 2.0 due to the record MCZ 50743, from within the EEZ, of *Bathytroctes alvifrons* Garman, 1899, now considered a junior synonym of *B. macrolepis*: it replaces the incorrect listing of *B. microlepis*, which is also present in the TEP (Robertson et al. 2017), but not confirmed in the Galapagos EEZ so far. *Bathytroctes macrolepis* was correctly listed in Tables 8 & 9 in Version 2.0, but incorrectly listed as “*B. microlepis*” in Tables 1 & 2 in Version 2.0 and in Version 1.0.

Leuroglossus stilbius (Bathylagidae) was misspelled as as *L. “stilbeus”* in Tables 1 & 2 in Version 2.0 (and correctly spelled in Tables 8 & 9).

Seriola rivoliana (Carangidae) was misspelled as as *S. “riviolana”* in Tables 1 & 2 in Version 2.0 (and correctly spelled in Version 1.0 and Version 2.0 Tables 5 & 9).

Cryptopsaras couesii (Ceratiidae) was misspelled as *C. “coueseii”* in Version 2.0.

Orthopristis cantharina (Haemulidae) was misspelled as *O. “cantharinus”* in Version 1.0 and *O. “cantherina”* in Tables 1,2 & 9 in Version 2.0 (and correctly spelled in Table 5).

Melamphaes laeviceps and *M. spinifer* (Melamphaidae) were misspelled as “*Melamphaeus*” in Tables 1,2 & 9 in Version 2.0 (and correctly spelled in Table 8).

Diaphus rafinesquii (Myctophidae) was misspelled as as *D. “rafenesquii”* in Version 1.0 and as *D. “rafenesqii”* in Version 2.0.

Hygophum reinhardtii (Myctophidae) was misspelled as as *H. “reinhardt”* in Version 1 and Tables 1,2 & 9 in Version 2.0 (and correctly spelled in Table 8).

Triphoturus oculus (Myctophidae) was misspelled as *T. “oculeum”* in Versions 1.0 & 2.0.

Vinciguerria lucetius (Phosichthyidae) was misspelled as *V. “lucetia”* in Versions 1.0 & 2.0.

Yarella argenteola (Phosichthyidae) was misspelled as “*Yarella argentiola*” in Tables 1, 2 & 9 in Version 2.0 ((and correctly spelled in Table 8).

Cololabis adoceta (Scomberesocidae) was misspelled as *C. “adocetus”* in Version 1 and Tables 1,2 & 9 in Version 2.0 (and correctly spelled in Table 7).

note: in Version 1.0, Grove et al. (2022) report “644 species of fishes, with 56 in Chondrichthyes and 576 bony fishes”; it should say “644 species of fishes, with 8 Myxiniiformes, 61 Chondrichthyes and 575 bony fishes”. The single cephalochordate was not included in 2022.

Taxonomic name changes

Poromitra crassiceps (Melamphaidae) in the TEP is changed to *P. cf. crassiceps* since Kotlyar (2024) defines *P. crassiceps* as an Atlantic species with a complex of sister species in other oceans. However, there are TEP mtDNA sequences identical to an Atlantic lineage listed as *P. crassiceps* (and there are additional widespread unnamed lineages within the complex).

Changes in resident or endemic status

Naso hexacanthus (Acanthuridae) is changed to resident from vagrant in Version 2.0 based on multiple recent records of individuals and groups of adults, at Seymour and Floreana (Bensted-Smith et al. 2025), as well as more recently at Wolf and Darwin (WBS at iNat). Fernando Rivera reports he observed 6 individuals at Floreana as far back as 2001. This widespread Indo-Pacific surgeonfish has been documented at Clipperton as multiple adults (Robertson & Allen 1997), is listed at Cocos Island (Cortés 2012, Fourrière et al. 2017), but with all listings tracing back to DRR's observation of three in 1997 (Robertson et. al. 2004), and observed and photographed at Guerrero and Oaxaca, Mexico by zoologist Ronald César Zepeta Vilchis (GBIF).

Atherinella nesiotus (Atherinopsidae) is corrected to endemic since the single record outside Galapagos, LACM 54500-8 (1) collected in 1937 by the R/V *Velero III* off Nayarit, Mexico, and listed in Fricke et al. (2024, p. 418), is not this species according to W.B. Ludt, Associate Curator at LACM (pers. comm.). The *A. nesiotus* from CAS 6039 has no collection date, only a note the ID was made by B. Chernoff in 1980. Otherwise there have been none collected in the past 60 years, since 1967, a concerning finding given the species is limited to the Galapagos.

Melichthys vidua (Balistidae) is changed to resident from vagrant in Version 2.0 based on the observation of a population of territorial adults at Islote Espejo, Marchena by WBS in February 2026.

Tylosurus fodiator (Belonidae) is changed back to resident from vagrant in Version 2.0 (it was resident in Version 1.0). A photograph from Gardner in iNat shows a school of large adults, consistent with a resident population.

Pseudonus acutus (Bythitidae) is changed to non-endemic, since there is a record from the Gulf of Panama identified by J. Nielsen in Denmark (NHMD 1559139).

Aluterus monoceros (Monacanthidae) is changed to resident from vagrant in Version 2.0 based on the reports of many individuals and schools in surveys by Rastoin-Laplane et al. (2023).

Opistognathus galapagensis (Opistognathidae) is corrected to non-endemic; the species was described by Allen & Robertson (1991) from specimens from both Galapagos and Costa Rica. Confusion was raised by McCosker's (1998) book review of Grove & Lavenburg (1997), where he mistakenly corrects the book's "*O. galapagensis* is not endemic... because it is known from other localities" followed with the phrase "but where?". Indeed, all three of McCosker's (1998) corrections to "endemic" are incorrect: *O. galapagensis*, *Quassiremus evionthas*, and *Symphurus diabolicus* (all are non-endemic).

Prionotus pictus Victor, 2025 (Triglidae), a newly described endemic species replaces the non-endemic *P. stephanophrys* (see above replacements section).

Other notes

Melanorhinus cyanellus (Atherinopsidae) is included in the list as a resident, however the collections in US museums are limited to a single specimen in LACM 45665 from the R/V *Velero III* surveys in 1932 and a pair in CAS 92296 from a nightlight off Isabela by the Templeton Crocker Expedition, also in 1932. These fish can be overlooked since they are small and share a bright silvery metallic color with the abundant juvenile mullets (Mugilidae) that can be collected with them. They may well prove to a very rare vagrant from continental waters if no other specimens are found.

Trachurus murphyi (Carangidae) is included in the lists: it was described from Peru and has very few records from the central equatorial region of the TEP, and some are from collections with poor provenance. However, USNM 236807 contains hundreds of individuals of *T. murphyi* collected off Fernandina by the R/V *Anton Bruun* expedition in 1966 (confirmed by photographs from USNM courtesy of Abigail Reft).

Carcharhinus melanopterus (Carcharinidae) is repeatedly reported from Galapagos, both as amateur observations and from photographs of sharks with some black on the tip of the dorsal fin (on observation.org and GBIF). However, *Carcharhinus limbatus* can show a limited area of black on the tip of the first dorsal fin and extending down as a streak along the rear margin of the fin, while *C. melanopterus* has a wider area of black on the dorsal fin, typically covering the distal third of the fin, underlined with a pale zone. *C. melanopterus* is widespread and common in the Indo-Pacific, but only recently has been recognized in the TEP. There is a published record of *C. melanopterus* at Cocos Island, as a juvenile in Wafer Bay, in López-Garro et al. (2012). Subsequently there has been regular observations and photographs of juveniles with extensive black areas on the dorsal fins in an apparent nursery area in the shallows in Wafer Bay (personal observation by author WBS). They have not been documented elsewhere in the region and the species is not included in the Galapagos species list.

Coryphaena equiselis and *C. hippurus* (Coryphaenidae) are moved from inshore pelagic to offshore pelagic, *Cyclopsetta querna* (Cyclopsettidae) is not included in the lists despite a photograph of the distinctive giant larva taken at Kicker Rock in San Cristobal, reported by Alex Hearn. Victor (2024) reported on a large collection of pelagic fish larvae from an open ocean site about midway between the continent and Galapagos, with some evidence suggesting the larvae may originate from as distant as the Bay of Panama. Fish larvae are apparently transported towards the Galapagos in vast numbers and at a high speed, yet many species do not establish populations in the Archipelago. If they do succeed in settling and are observed rarely, they would qualify as vagrants. Accepting larvae as records would greatly distort species lists since dozens, even hundreds, of species of continental and catadromous freshwater fish larvae can be collected in plankton trawls in the region, including at the margins of the Galapagos EEZ (Victor 2024).

Dactylagnus mundus (Dactyloscopidae) has not been included in the lists but has been reported from the Galapagos based on a single record CAS 14204, from the *Zaca* expedition in 1932 (Grove & Lavenberg 1997). However the CAS catalog presently identifies the specimen as *Myxodagnus opercularis* (it should be noted that the Galapagos population of *Myxodagnus* should be considered the endemic *Myxodagnus sagitta* Myers & Wade, 1946). All subsequent Galapagos specimens of *Myxodagnus* in the CAS catalog are listed as *M. sagitta*.

Haemulon sexfasciatum (Haemulidae) is an episodic resident, it had been reported in early surveys, with a school photographed in 2002 (iNat), but has apparently not been observed underwater in Galapagos since then, until author IK recently photographed a single large adult within a school of *Anisotremus espinozai* at Bartolome. Prior unconfirmed observations may have followed from the misidentification of *Orthopristis cantharina* as *H. sexfasciatum* in guidebooks, by Constant (2007, p. 96) and Humann & DeLoach (1993, p. 57), the latter corrected in their second edition (Humann & DeLoach 2003, p. 65).

Stethojulis bandanensis (Labridae) is also an episodic resident which can arrive in large numbers during the ENSO months and then subsequently dwindle over years and become rare (Victor et al. 2001).

Asthenomacrus fragilis (Macrouridae) is known from the Bay of Panama and off Colombia and a single station west of Galapagos at 00°02'S, 100°23'W, well beyond the Galapagos EEZ. The map in the FAO chapter in 1995 (Iwamoto & Schneider 1995, p. 1261) shifts the dot to 90° W, i.e. directly over the Galapagos. Notably, *A. fragilis* is not included in the list of macrourids of Galapagos in the more recent Iwamoto & McCosker (2001). Sources such as FishBase have followed the FAO chapter printing error and added Galapagos to the collection locations for the species. The species is quite likely to be found in Galapagos since it lies between the two sites, however, the record is not within the EEZ and we do not include the species in the list.

Nezumia orbitalis (Macrouridae) is known from Panama and Peru. Only one reference includes Galapagos, i.e. the map in the FAO chapter in 1995 (Iwamoto & Schneider 1995, p. 1265). However, *N. orbitalis* is not included in the list of macrourids of Galapagos in the more recent Iwamoto & McCosker (2001). The FAO chapter text says the range is “Panama and Peru”, but the map shows only three dots: off Panama and centered on Galapagos and the third on the eastern edge of the Galapagos EEZ, with no dot off Peru. Since the species is not included in Iwamoto’s Galapagos list from 2001, and there are no Galapagos records in any of the online collection databases, we believe the FAO map is another printing error, and thus do not include the species in the list.

Poromitra megalops (Melamphaidae) records in the TEP are *P. jucunda*, with the SIO record (SIO 05-154) apparently corresponding to the circle for *P. jucunda* at Galapagos in Fig. 30 in Kotlyar (2024).

Diaphus longleyi Fowler, 1934 (Myctophidae) (described from Philippines) is reported in SIO 71-351, however the validity of that species is questionable: the Catalog of Fishes considers it a synonym of *D. parri* Tåning, 1932 described from the western Pacific and widespread in the Indo-Pacific (Fricke et al. 2026), but so far not the eastern Pacific. It is not added to the list pending confirmation.

Encheliophis vermicularis (Ophidiidae: Carapinae) is listed for the Galapagos since a single adult was described from Tagus Cove under the name *Encheliophis jordani* Heller & Snodgrass, 1903 (they did not mention sea cucumbers). This species is a commensal of holothurians, and one would expect them to be collected from the millions of sea cucumbers that have been harvested from the Archipelago, none of which has apparently yielded a single specimen for any scientists. However, many have been collected in the lower Sea of Cortez, (several SIO collections), both from shallow sea cucumbers and from deep otter trawls (at 40 fathoms in SIO 65-294). Curiously, no vexillifer (pre-settlement) larva identified as this species (or genus) have ever been collected anywhere (Markle & Olney 1990), and they conclude that they must be included in larvae identified as *Carapus* (they propose for vexillifer larvae, the appropriate identification should be *Carapus/Encheliophis*). DNA should resolve the issue as TEP carapid larvae are sequenced; all of the barcoded larvae from Victor (2024) were *Echiodon exsilium*.

Echiodon exsilium (Ophidiidae: Carapinae) is a pearlfish which is free-living rather than commensal within the gut of sea cucumbers or inside other invertebrates. Almost all regional specimens are larvae collected in plankton tows: indeed, all but one of the 6 individuals (at CAS and SIO) are from towed nets. Three of the specimens are from the 1925 *Arcturus* expedition. A set of 12 larvae from 36–115 mm were captured in the larval collections over the Galapagos hydrothermal vents (Victor 2024). CAS 86743 is a benthic specimen collected by John McCosker at 468 m depth from the Johnson-Sea-Link submersible off Santa Cruz in 1995. Markle & Olney (1990) indicate both larval and adult specimens are from Galapagos (p. 350 & Fig. 70), but do not provide that provenance.

Bassozetus nasus Garman, 1899 (Ophidiidae) is the only species of the genus known from the TEP, with the holotype reported from off Colombia, near Malpelo Island. Cohen & Haedrich (1983) list *Bassozetus* as abundant in their reports of abyssal vent-associated fishes at the Galapagos hydrothermal vents, however no specimens of any *Bassozetus* have been collected or confirmed photographs taken within the EEZ and thus the species is not added to the list. Two putative species of *Bassozetus* sp. were photographed at 7° S, beyond the Galapagos EEZ (Drazen et al. 2019, Fig. 2). There is little doubt some species should be found in Galapagos waters, but the taxonomy needs additional collections and review to resolve its status.

Argyropelecus hemigymnus (Sternoptychidae) has not been included in the lists but has been reported from near Galapagos by GBIF based on LACM 4707, along with several other LACM records in the region, including 4 from the R/V *Velero* off Costa Rica and several more from far to the west. However, LACM metadata for all of those specimens list them as “sp.” which is creatively interpreted by GBIF as a novel species “*Argyropelecus spec* Valenciennes, 1849”, a name that does not exist, and GBIF adds that it is a “synonym of *A. hemigymnus*” – which it is not. In fact, there are apparently no real records of the anti-tropical *A. hemigymnus* in the eastern Pacific, raising an issue for the isolated specimen CAS 46714, listed as *A. hemigymnus* in their catalog. It was collected south of Cocos by the R/V *Arcturus* 1925 expedition. In Beebe’s (1926) book of the *Arcturus* Expedition, there is a color engraving of “*Aryropelecus*” as Fig. A; and on p. 347 it indicates the hatchetfish had been collected at the same location and day as CAS 46714. The illustrated specimen is not *A. hemigymnus*, which has prominent gaps in the ventral line of photophores; in contrast, it has a continuous ventral line more consistent with *A. sladeni* or *A. olfersii*. Of the 7 valid species listed in Fricke et al. (2026), 6 are considered circumglobal and *A. lychnus* is endemic to the eastern Pacific from California to Chile. Love et al. (2021) list only 5 in the region (not including *A. olfersii* or *A. gigas*). Records of *A. gigas* are solely temperate in the eastern Pacific. Our list includes *A. olfersii* based on numerous museum specimens.

Aristostomias xenostoma (Stomiidae) is not in the list, although there is a single record in the Denmark museum, NHMD 1479313, from the R/V *Dana II* 1928 expedition, putatively from within the Costa Rican EEZ off Cocos Island (2.9°, -87.6°). However, no other *Aristostomias* have been recorded nearer Galapagos, or indeed in a broad band of the equatorial eastern Pacific Ocean south of Mexican waters. The metadata for the record does not indicate the source of the identification.

Introduced freshwater fishes (not included in list)

Oreochromis niloticus (Nile Tilapia) were illegally introduced into Laguna El Junco on San Cristóbal Island in 2005. Subsequently, Nico & Walsh (2011) report on the eradication of the population using rotenone in 2008, with tens of thousands of Tilapia removed from the lake.

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TABLE B

List of Fishes removed/not accepted from the Galapagos species list
Simple taxonomic name changes not included (version number indicated)

Species	Family	Version	Species	Family	Version
<i>Alopias vulpinus</i>	Alopiidae	2.0	<i>Remora australis</i>	Echeneidae	2.0
<i>Carcharhinus melanopterus</i>	Carcharhinidae	3.0	<i>Cypselurus angusticeps</i>	Exocoetidae	2.0
<i>Sphyrna mokarran</i>	Sphyrnidae	2.0	<i>Hirundichthys rondeletii</i>	Exocoetidae	2.0
<i>Sphyrna tiburo</i>	Sphyrnidae	2.0	<i>Parexocoetus brachypterus</i>	Exocoetidae	2.0
<i>Myliobatis longirostris</i>	Myliobatidae	2.0	<i>Prognichthys sealei</i>	Exocoetidae	2.0
<i>Chimaera</i> sp.	Chimaeridae	2.0	<i>Prognichthys tringa</i>	Exocoetidae	2.0
<i>Bathycongrus</i> sp.	Congridae	2.0	<i>Ekemblemaria</i> sp.	Chaenopsidae	2.0
<i>Chilochongrus dentatus</i>	Congridae	2.0	<i>Dactylagnus mundus</i>	Dactyloscopidae	3.0
<i>Gnathophis cinctus</i>	Congridae	2.0	<i>Cookeolus japonicus</i>	Priacanthidae	2.0
<i>Japonoconger</i> n. sp.	Congridae	2.0	<i>Priacanthus</i> sp.	Priacanthidae	2.0
<i>Bathytroctes microlepis</i>	Alepocephalidae	3.0	<i>Cilus gilberti</i>	Sciaenidae	2.0
<i>Argyropelecus hemigymnus</i>	Sternoptychidae	3.0	<i>Cynoscion phoxocephalus</i>	Sciaenidae	2.0
<i>Aristostomias xenostoma</i>	Stomiidae	3.0	<i>Mycteroperca xenarcha</i>	Epinephelidae	2.0
<i>Astronesthes martensii</i>	Stomiidae	2.0	<i>Diplectrum euryplectrum</i>	Serranidae	2.0
<i>Stomias boa</i>	Stomiidae	2.0	<i>Diplectrum macropoma</i>	Serranidae	2.0
<i>Diaphus longleyi</i>	Myctophidae	3.0	<i>Diplectrum maximum</i>	Serranidae	2.0
<i>Bregmaceros macclellandi</i>	Bregmacerotidae	2.0	<i>Diplectrum pacificum</i>	Serranidae	2.0
<i>Merluccius gayi</i>	Merlucciidae	2.0	<i>Paralabrax humeralis</i>	Serranidae	2.0
<i>Asthenomacrus fragilis</i>	Macrouridae	3.0	<i>Halichoeres melanotis</i>	Labridae	3.0
<i>Nezumia orbitalis</i>	Macrouridae	3.0	<i>Peristedion barbiger</i>	Triglidae	2.0
<i>Poromitra megalops</i>	Melamphaidae	3.0	<i>Prionotus stephanophrys</i>	Triglidae	3.0
<i>Bassozetus nasus</i>	Ophidiidae	3.0	<i>Pontinus</i> sp. A	Scorpaenidae	2.0
<i>Carapus mourlani</i>	Ophidiidae	3.0	<i>Pontinus</i> sp. B	Scorpaenidae	2.0
<i>Ogilbia ventralis</i>	Dinematichthyidae	2.0	<i>Pontinus</i> sp. C	Scorpaenidae	2.0
<i>Porichthys margaritatus</i>	Batrachoididae	2.0	<i>Pontinus strigatus</i>	Scorpaenidae	2.0
<i>Thunnus alalunga</i>	Scombridae	2.0	<i>Pontinus vaughani</i>	Scorpaenidae	2.0
<i>Bollmannia macropoma</i>	Gobiidae	2.0	<i>Abantennarius coccineus</i>	Antennariidae	2.0
<i>Sphyrna helleri</i>	Sphyrnidae	2.0	<i>Mola mola</i>	Molidae	2.0
<i>Cyclosetta querna</i>	Cyclosettidae	3.0	<i>Ranzania laevis</i>	Molidae	2.0
<i>Nematistius pectoralis</i>	Nematistiidae	2.0	<i>Diodon eydouxii</i>	Diodontidae	3.0

TABLE 1 (p. 1)

Fishes of the Galapagos Archipelago
(719 spp. in taxonomic order)

Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Branchiostomus elongatus</i>	Branchiostomatidae	R	<i>Centrophorus squamosus</i>	Centrophoridae	R
<i>Eptatretus goslinaei</i>	Myxinidae	RE	<i>Echinorhinus cookei</i>	Echinorhinidae	R
<i>Eptatretus grouseri</i>	Myxinidae	RE	<i>Tetronarce tremens</i>	Torpedinidae	R
<i>Eptatretus mccoskeri</i>	Myxinidae	RE	<i>Pseudobatos planiceps</i>	Rhinobatidae	R
<i>Eptatretus bobwisneri</i>	Myxinidae	RE	<i>Rajella eisenhardti</i>	Rajidae	RE
<i>Myxine greggi</i>	Myxinidae	RE	<i>Rostroraja velezi</i>	Rajidae	R
<i>Myxine martinii</i>	Myxinidae	RE	<i>Bathyraja abyssicola</i>	Arhynchobatidae	R
<i>Myxine phantasma</i>	Myxinidae	RE	<i>Bathyraja peruana</i>	Arhynchobatidae	R
<i>Rubicundus lakeside</i>	Myxinidae	RE	<i>Bathyraja richardsoni</i>	Arhynchobatidae	R
<i>Hexanchus griseus</i>	Hexanchidae	R	<i>Bathyraja spinosissima</i>	Arhynchobatidae	R
<i>Notorynchus cepedianus</i>	Hexanchidae	R	<i>Gurgesiella furvescens</i>	Gurgesiellidae	R
<i>Heterodontus quoyi</i>	Heterodontidae	R	<i>Hypanus dipterurus</i>	Dasyatidae	R
<i>Rhincodon typus</i>	Rhincodontidae	R	<i>Hypanus longus</i>	Dasyatidae	R
<i>Odontaspis ferox</i>	Odontaspidae	R	<i>Pteroplatytrygon violacea</i>	Dasyatidae	R
<i>Alopias pelagicus</i>	Alopiidae	R	<i>Taeniurops meyeri</i>	Dasyatidae	R
<i>Alopias superciliosus</i>	Alopiidae	R	<i>Styracura pacifica</i>	Potamotrygonidae	R
<i>Carcharodon carcharias</i>	Lamnidae	V	<i>Aetobatus ocellatus</i>	Aetobatidae	R
<i>Isurus oxyrinchus</i>	Lamnidae	R	<i>Aetomylaeus asperrimus</i>	Myliobatidae	V
<i>Bythaelurus giddingsi</i>	Scyliorhinidae	RE	<i>Myliobatis peruviana</i>	Myliobatidae	R
<i>Galeus</i> n. sp.	Scyliorhinidae	RE	<i>Rhinoptera steindachneri</i>	Rhinopteridae	R
<i>Apristurus kampae</i>	Pentanchidae	R	<i>Mobula birostris</i>	Mobulidae	R
<i>Apristurus</i> n. sp.	Pentanchidae	RE	<i>Mobula mobular</i>	Mobulidae	R
<i>Mustelus albipinnis</i>	Triakidae	R	<i>Mobula munkiana</i>	Mobulidae	R
<i>Mustelus mento</i>	Triakidae	R	<i>Mobula tarapacana</i>	Mobulidae	R
<i>Triakis maculata</i>	Triakidae	R	<i>Mobula thurstoni</i>	Mobulidae	R
<i>Carcharhinus albimarginatus</i>	Carcharhinidae	R	<i>Hydrolagus alphas</i>	Chimaeridae	RE
<i>Carcharhinus altimus</i>	Carcharhinidae	R	<i>Hydrolagus mccoskeri</i>	Chimaeridae	RE
<i>Carcharhinus amblyrhynchos</i>	Carcharhinidae	V	<i>Hydrolagus melanophasma</i>	Chimaeridae	R
<i>Carcharhinus falciformis</i>	Carcharhinidae	R	<i>Hydrolagus</i> n. sp.	Chimaeridae	RE
<i>Carcharhinus galapagensis</i>	Carcharhinidae	R	<i>Elops affinis</i>	Elopidae	V
<i>Carcharhinus limbatus</i>	Carcharhinidae	R	<i>Albula esuncula</i>	Albulidae	V
<i>Carcharhinus longimanus</i>	Carcharhinidae	R	<i>Halosaurus attenuatus</i>	Halosauridae	R
<i>Nasolamia velox</i>	Carcharhinidae	R	<i>Notacanthus spinosus</i>	Notacanthidae	R
<i>Prionace glauca</i>	Carcharhinidae	R	<i>Ilyophis arx</i>	Synphobranchidae	R
<i>Triaenodon obesus</i>	Carcharhinidae	R	<i>Ilyophis brunneus</i>	Synphobranchidae	R
<i>Galeocerdo cuvier</i>	Galeocerdonidae	R	<i>Myroconger nigrodentatus</i>	Myrocongridae	R
<i>Sphyrna lewini</i>	Sphyrnidae	R	<i>Anarchias galapagensis</i>	Muraenidae	R
<i>Sphyrna zygaena</i>	Sphyrnidae	R	<i>Echidna nebulosa</i>	Muraenidae	R
<i>Isistius brasiliensis</i>	Dalatiidae	R	<i>Echidna nocturna</i>	Muraenidae	R
<i>Centroscyllium nigrum</i>	Etmopteridae	R	<i>Enchelycore lichenosa</i>	Muraenidae	R

TABLE 1 (p. 2)

Fishes of the Galapagos Archipelago

Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Enchelycore octaviana</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Xenomystax atrarius</i>	Congridae	R
<i>Gymnomuraena zebra</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Avocettina infans</i>	Nemichthyidae	R
<i>Gymnothorax angusticeps</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Nemichthys scolopaceus</i>	Nemichthyidae	R
<i>Gymnothorax buroensis</i>	Muraenidae	V	<i>Serrivomer sector</i>	Serrivomeridae	R
<i>Gymnothorax castaneus</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Anguilla marmorata</i>	Anguillidae	R
<i>Gymnothorax dovii</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Anchoa argentivittata</i>	Engraulidae	R
<i>Gymnothorax flavimarginatus</i>	Muraenidae	V	<i>Anchoa ischana</i>	Engraulidae	R
<i>Gymnothorax javanicus</i>	Muraenidae	V	<i>Cetengraulis mysticetus</i>	Engraulidae	V
<i>Gymnothorax meleagris</i>	Muraenidae	V	<i>Engraulis ringens</i>	Engraulidae	R
<i>Gymnothorax panamensis</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Harengula thrissina</i>	Clupeidae	R
<i>Gymnothorax pictus</i>	Muraenidae	V	<i>Lile stolifera</i>	Clupeidae	R
<i>Gymnothorax porphyreus</i>	Muraenidae	V	<i>Opisthonema berlangai</i>	Clupeidae	RE
<i>Gymnothorax undulatus</i>	Muraenidae	V	<i>Opisthonema libertate</i>	Clupeidae	R
<i>Muraena argus</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Etrumeus acuminatus</i>	Dussumeriidae	R
<i>Muraena clepsydra</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Sardinops sagax</i>	Alosidae	R
<i>Muraena lentiginosa</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Bathytroctes macrolepis</i>	Alepocephalidae	R
<i>Scuticaria tigrina</i>	Muraenidae	V	<i>Einara macrolepis</i>	Alepocephalidae	R
<i>Uropterygius macrocephalus</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Narctes erimelas</i>	Alepocephalidae	R
<i>Uropterygius polystictus</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Photostylus pycnopterus</i>	Alepocephalidae	R
<i>Uropterygius versutus</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Holtbyrnia latifrons</i>	Platyroctidae	R
<i>Chlopsis bicollaris</i>	Chlopsidae	R	<i>Maulisia isaaci</i>	Platyroctidae	R
<i>Apterichthys equatorialis</i>	Ophichthidae	R	<i>Platyroctes apus</i>	Platyroctidae	R
<i>Bascanichthys bascanoides</i>	Ophichthidae	R	<i>Sagamichthys abei</i>	Platyroctidae	R
<i>Callechelys galapagensis</i>	Ophichthidae	RE	<i>Chanos chanos</i>	Chanidae	R
<i>Herpetoichthys fossatus</i>	Ophichthidae	R	<i>Argentina alicae</i>	Argentinidae	R
<i>Ichthyapus selachops</i>	Ophichthidae	R	<i>Bathylagoides nigrigenys</i>	Bathylagidae	R
<i>Myrichthys xysturus</i>	Ophichthidae	R	<i>Bathylagus wesethi</i>	Bathylagidae	R
<i>Ophichthus arneutes</i>	Ophichthidae	RE	<i>Leuroglossus stilbius</i>	Bathylagidae	R
<i>Ophichthus rugifer</i>	Ophichthidae	R	<i>Bathylchnops sp.</i>	Opisthoproctidae	R
<i>Paraetharchus opercularis</i>	Ophichthidae	R	<i>Dolichopteryx pseudolongipes</i>	Opisthoproctidae	R
<i>Phaenomonas pinnata</i>	Ophichthidae	R	<i>Cyclothone acclinidens</i>	Gonostomatidae	R
<i>Quassiremus evionthas</i>	Ophichthidae	R	<i>Cyclothone alba</i>	Gonostomatidae	R
<i>Scytalichthys miurus</i>	Ophichthidae	V	<i>Cyclothone atraria</i>	Gonostomatidae	R
<i>Facciolella equatorialis</i>	Nettastomatidae	R	<i>Cyclothone braueri</i>	Gonostomatidae	R
<i>Ariosoma gilberti</i>	Congridae	R	<i>Cyclothone microdon</i>	Gonostomatidae	R
<i>Bathycongrus varidens</i>	Congridae	R	<i>Cyclothone obscura</i>	Gonostomatidae	R
<i>Heteroconger klausewitzi</i>	Congridae	R	<i>Cyclothone pallida</i>	Gonostomatidae	R
<i>Japonoconger proriger</i>	Congridae	R	<i>Cyclothone pseudopallida</i>	Gonostomatidae	R
<i>Paraconger californiensis</i>	Congridae	R	<i>Cyclothone signata</i>	Gonostomatidae	R
<i>Paraconger similis</i>	Congridae	R	<i>Diplophos proximus</i>	Gonostomatidae	R

TABLE 1 (p. 3)

Fishes of the Galapagos Archipelago

Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Sigmops elongatus</i>	Gonostomatidae	R	<i>Rosenblattichthys volucris</i>	Scopelarchidae	R
<i>Argyropelecus aculeatus</i>	Sternoptychidae	R	<i>Scopelarchoides nicholsi</i>	Scopelarchidae	R
<i>Argyropelecus affinis</i>	Sternoptychidae	R	<i>Scopelarchus guentheri</i>	Scopelarchidae	R
<i>Argyropelecus lychnus</i>	Sternoptychidae	R	<i>Scopelosaurus harryi</i>	Notosudidae	R
<i>Argyropelecus olfersii</i>	Sternoptychidae	R	<i>Scopelosaurus hubbsi</i>	Notosudidae	R
<i>Argyropelecus sladeni</i>	Sternoptychidae	R	<i>Synodus lacertinus</i>	Synodontidae	R
<i>Danaphos oculatus</i>	Sternoptychidae	R	<i>Synodus scituliceps</i>	Synodontidae	R
<i>Maurollicus australis</i>	Sternoptychidae	R	<i>Synodus sechurae</i>	Synodontidae	R
<i>Sternoptyx diaphana</i>	Sternoptychidae	R	<i>Lestidiops pacificus</i>	Paralepididae	R
<i>Sternoptyx obscura</i>	Sternoptychidae	R	<i>Lestidium bigelowi</i>	Paralepididae	R
<i>Sternoptyx pseudobscura</i>	Sternoptychidae	R	<i>Stemonosudis macrura</i>	Paralepididae	R
<i>Valencienellus tripunctulatus</i>	Sternoptychidae	R	<i>Evermannella ahlstromi</i>	Evermannellidae	R
<i>Ichthyococcus irregularis</i>	Phosichthyidae	R	<i>Scopelengys tristis</i>	Neoscopelidae	R
<i>Vinciguerria lucetius</i>	Phosichthyidae	R	<i>Bolinichthys longipes</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Vinciguerria nimbaria</i>	Phosichthyidae	R	<i>Centrobranchus andreae</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Vinciguerria poweriae</i>	Phosichthyidae	R	<i>Centrobranchus nigroocellatus</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Yarella argenteola</i>	Phosichthyidae	R	<i>Dasyscopelus asper</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Astronesthes cyanea</i>	Stomiidae	R	<i>Diaphus fulgens</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Astronesthes galapagensis</i>	Stomiidae	R	<i>Diaphus mollis</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Astronesthes gibbsi</i>	Stomiidae	R	<i>Diaphus pacificus</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Astronesthes indica</i>	Stomiidae	R	<i>Diaphus parri</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Astronesthes lampara</i>	Stomiidae	R	<i>Diaphus rafinesquii</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Bathophilus filifer</i>	Stomiidae	R	<i>Diaphus termophilus</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Borostomias elucens</i>	Stomiidae	R	<i>Diaphus theta</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Borostomias panamensis</i>	Stomiidae	R	<i>Diogenichthys laternatus</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Chauliodus barbatus</i>	Stomiidae	R	<i>Gonichthys tenuiculus</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Chauliodus sloani</i>	Stomiidae	R	<i>Gonichthys venetus</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Idiacanthus antrostomus</i>	Stomiidae	R	<i>Hygophum reinhardtii</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Malacosteus niger</i>	Stomiidae	R	<i>Lampadena luminosa</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Photonectes margarita</i>	Stomiidae	R	<i>Lampanyctus crypticus</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Stomias atriventer</i>	Stomiidae	R	<i>Lampanyctus hubbsi</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Stomias colubrinus</i>	Stomiidae	R	<i>Lampanyctus idostigma</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Stomias danae</i>	Stomiidae	R	<i>Lampanyctus macropterus</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Thysanactis dentex</i>	Stomiidae	R	<i>Lampanyctus nobilis</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Guentherus altivela</i>	Ateleopodidae	R	<i>Lampanyctus omostigma</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Aulopus chirichignoae</i>	Aulopidae	R	<i>Lampanyctus parvicauda</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Chlorophthalmus mento</i>	Chlorophthalmidae	R	<i>Lampanyctus ritteri</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Bathypterois atricolor</i>	Ipnopidae	R	<i>Lampanyctus tenuiformis</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Bathypterois pectinatus</i>	Ipnopidae	R	<i>Loweina rara</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Ipnops agassizii</i>	Ipnopidae	R	<i>Myctophum affine</i>	Myctophidae	R

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Fishes of the Galapagos Archipelago

Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Myctophum aurolaternatum</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Poromitra cf. crassiceps</i>	Melamphaidae	R
<i>Myctophum brachygnathum</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Poromitra frontosa</i>	Melamphaidae	R
<i>Myctophum nitidulum</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Poromitra jucunda</i>	Melamphaidae	R
<i>Notolychnus valdiviae</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Poromitra nigrofulva</i>	Melamphaidae	R
<i>Notoscopelus elongatus</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Poromitra oscitans</i>	Melamphaidae	R
<i>Notoscopelus resplendens</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Scopeloberyx opisthopterus</i>	Melamphaidae	R
<i>Protomyctophum</i> sp.	Myctophidae	R	<i>Scopeloberyx robustus</i>	Melamphaidae	R
<i>Symbolophorus evermanni</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Scopelogadus bispinosus</i>	Melamphaidae	R
<i>Symbolophorus reversus</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Rondeletia loricata</i>	Rondeletiidae	R
<i>Triphoturus mexicanus</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Cetomimus gillii</i>	Cetomimidae	R
<i>Triphoturus nigricans</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Hoplostethus pacificus</i>	Trachichthyidae	RE
<i>Triphoturus oculus</i>	Myctophidae	R	<i>Anoplogaster cornuta</i>	Anoplogastridae	R
<i>Desmodema polystictum</i>	Trachipteridae	R	<i>Myripristis berndti</i>	Holocentridae	R
<i>Zu cristatus</i>	Trachipteridae	R	<i>Myripristis leiognathus</i>	Holocentridae	R
<i>Regalecus russellii</i>	Regalacidae	R	<i>Neoniphon suborbitalis</i>	Holocentridae	R
<i>Stylephorus chordatus</i>	Stylephoridae	R	<i>Bathyonus caudalis</i>	Ophidiidae	R
<i>Bregmaceros bathymaster</i>	Bregmacerotidae	V	<i>Brotula ordwayi</i>	Ophidiidae	R
<i>Trachyrincus helolepis</i>	Trachyrincidae	R	<i>Dicrolene nigra</i>	Ophidiidae	R
<i>Antimora rostrata</i>	Moridae	R	<i>Echiodon exsilium</i>	Ophidiidae	R
<i>Gadella filifer</i>	Moridae	R	<i>Encheliophis vermicularis</i>	Ophidiidae	R
<i>Gadella thysthlon</i>	Moridae	RE	<i>Eretmichthys pinnatus</i>	Ophidiidae	R
<i>Laemonema gracillipes</i>	Moridae	R	<i>Lamprogrammus niger</i>	Ophidiidae	R
<i>Physiculus nematopus</i>	Moridae	R	<i>Lepohidium pardale</i>	Ophidiidae	R
<i>Coelorinchus canus</i>	Macrouridae	R	<i>Monomitopus malispinosus</i>	Ophidiidae	R
<i>Coryphaenoides anguliceps</i>	Macrouridae	R	<i>Monomitopus torvus</i>	Ophidiidae	R
<i>Coryphaenoides armatus</i>	Macrouridae	R	<i>Ophidion galapagensis</i>	Ophidiidae	R
<i>Coryphaenoides boops</i>	Macrouridae	R	<i>Otophidium indefatigabile</i>	Ophidiidae	R
<i>Coryphaenoides bucephalus</i>	Macrouridae	R	<i>Porogadus promelas</i>	Ophidiidae	R
<i>Coryphaenoides bulbiceps</i>	Macrouridae	R	<i>Spectrunculus crassus</i>	Ophidiidae	R
<i>Coryphaenoides delsolari</i>	Macrouridae	R	<i>Bellottia</i> sp.	Bythitidae	R
<i>Coryphaenoides gypsochilus</i>	Macrouridae	RE	<i>Calamopteryx jeb</i>	Bythitidae	RE
<i>Coryphaenoides myersi</i>	Macrouridae	RE	<i>Cataetx rubirostris</i>	Bythitidae	R
<i>Mataeocephalus tenuicauda</i>	Macrouridae	R	<i>Cataetx simus</i>	Bythitidae	R
<i>Nezumia convergens</i>	Macrouridae	R	<i>Diplacanthopoma jordani</i>	Bythitidae	R
<i>Nezumia loricata</i>	Macrouridae	RE	<i>Grammonus diagrammus</i>	Bythitidae	R
<i>Nezumia parini</i>	Macrouridae	R	<i>Lucifuga inopinata</i>	Bythitidae	RE
<i>Nezumia stelgidolepis</i>	Macrouridae	R	<i>Petrotyx hopkinsi</i>	Bythitidae	R
<i>Nezumia ventralis</i>	Macrouridae	RE	<i>Pseudonus acutus</i>	Bythitidae	R
<i>Melamphaes laeviceps</i>	Melamphaidae	R	<i>Thermichthys hollisi</i>	Bythitidae	RE
<i>Melamphaes spinifer</i>	Melamphaidae	R	<i>Ogilbia deroyi</i>	Dinematichthyidae	RE

TABLE 1 (p. 5)

Fishes of the Galapagos Archipelago

Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Ogilbia galapagosensis</i>	Dinematchthyidae	RE	<i>Fistularia corneta</i>	Fistulariidae	V
<i>Seriolella violacea</i>	Centrolophidae	R	<i>Bryx veleronis</i>	Syngnathidae	R
<i>Cubiceps baxteri</i>	Nomeidae	R	<i>Cosmocampus coccineus</i>	Syngnathidae	R
<i>Cubiceps pauciradiatus</i>	Nomeidae	R	<i>Doryrhamphus melanopleura</i>	Syngnathidae	R
<i>Nomeus gronovii</i>	Nomeidae	R	<i>Hippocampus ingens</i>	Syngnathidae	R
<i>Psenes arafurensis</i>	Nomeidae	R	<i>Apogon atradorsatus</i>	Apogonidae	R
<i>Psenes cyanophrys</i>	Nomeidae	R	<i>Apogon dovii</i>	Apogonidae	R
<i>Psenes pellucidus</i>	Nomeidae	R	<i>Apogon pacificus</i>	Apogonidae	R
<i>Psenes sio</i>	Nomeidae	R	<i>Dormitator latifrons</i>	Eleotridae	V
<i>Tetragonurus atlanticus</i>	Tetragonuridae	R	<i>Eleotris picta</i>	Eleotridae	V
<i>Peprilus medius</i>	Stromateidae	R	<i>Gobiomorus maculatus</i>	Eleotridae	V
<i>Chiasmodon niger</i>	Chiasmodontidae	R	<i>Bathygobius lineatus</i>	Gobiidae	R
<i>Chiasmodon subniger</i>	Chiasmodontidae	R	<i>Chriolepis tagus</i>	Gobiidae	RE
<i>Acanthocybium solandri</i>	Scombridae	R	<i>Clarkichthys bilineatus</i>	Gobiidae	R
<i>Auxis rochei</i>	Scombridae	R	<i>Coryphopterus urospilus</i>	Gobiidae	R
<i>Auxis thazard</i>	Scombridae	R	<i>Eleotrica cableae</i>	Gobiidae	RE
<i>Euthynnus lineatus</i>	Scombridae	R	<i>Evorthodus minutus</i>	Gobiidae	V
<i>Katsuwonus pelamis</i>	Scombridae	R	<i>Lythrypnus gilberti</i>	Gobiidae	RE
<i>Sarda orientalis</i>	Scombridae	R	<i>Lythrypnus rhizophora</i>	Gobiidae	R
<i>Scomber japonicus</i>	Scombridae	R	<i>Microdesmus dipus</i>	Gobiidae	V
<i>Scomberomorus sierra</i>	Scombridae	R	<i>Schindleria praematura</i>	Gobiidae	R
<i>Thunnus albacares</i>	Scombridae	R	<i>Tigrigobius nesiotes</i>	Gobiidae	R
<i>Thunnus obesus</i>	Scombridae	R	<i>Centropomus viridis</i>	Centropomidae	R
<i>Paracaristius</i> sp.	Caristiidae	R	<i>Sphyraena barracuda</i>	Sphyraenidae	V
<i>Brama dussumieri</i>	Bramidae	R	<i>Sphyraena idiaestes</i>	Sphyraenidae	R
<i>Brama japonica</i>	Bramidae	V	<i>Sphyraena stellata</i>	Sphyraenidae	R
<i>Taractes rubescens</i>	Bramidae	R	<i>Polydactylus approximans</i>	Polynemidae	V
<i>Gempylus serpens</i>	Gempylidae	R	<i>Citharichthys darwini</i>	Cyclopsettidae	RE
<i>Lepidocybium flavobrunneum</i>	Gempylidae	R	<i>Citharichthys gnathus</i>	Cyclopsettidae	R
<i>Nealotus tripes</i>	Gempylidae	R	<i>Syacium latifrons</i>	Cyclopsettidae	V
<i>Ruvettus pretiosus</i>	Gempylidae	R	<i>Syacium maculiferum</i>	Cyclopsettidae	V
<i>Aphanopus capricornis</i>	Trichiuridae	R	<i>Bothus leopardinus</i>	Bothidae	R
<i>Benthodesmus tenuis</i>	Trichiuridae	R	<i>Bothus mancus</i>	Bothidae	R
<i>Lepidopus manis</i>	Trichiuridae	R	<i>Monolene maculipinna</i>	Bothidae	V
<i>Trichiurus nitens</i>	Trichiuridae	R	<i>Hippoglossina bollmani</i>	Paralichthyidae	R
<i>Mulloidichthys dentatus</i>	Mullidae	R	<i>Paralichthys woolmani</i>	Paralichthyidae	R
<i>Pseudupeneus grandisquamis</i>	Mullidae	R	<i>Trinectes fonsecensis</i>	Achiridae	V
<i>Synchiropus atrilabiatus</i>	Callionymidae	R	<i>Aseraggodes herrei</i>	Soleidae	R
<i>Aulostomus chinensis</i>	Aulostomidae	R	<i>Symphurus atramentatus</i>	Cynoglossidae	R
<i>Fistularia commersonii</i>	Fistulariidae	R	<i>Symphurus diabolicus</i>	Cynoglossidae	R

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Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Symphurus varius</i>	Cynoglossidae	R	<i>Coryphaena equiselis</i>	Coryphaenidae	R
<i>Xiphias gladius</i>	Xiphiidae	R	<i>Coryphaena hippurus</i>	Coryphaenidae	R
<i>Istiompax indica</i>	Istiophoridae	R	<i>Opistognathus galapagensis</i>	Opistognathidae	R
<i>Istiophorus platypterus</i>	Istiophoridae	R	<i>Abudefduf concolor</i>	Pomacentridae	R
<i>Kajikia audax</i>	Istiophoridae	R	<i>Abudefduf troschelii</i>	Pomacentridae	R
<i>Makaira nigricans</i>	Istiophoridae	R	<i>Azurina atrilobata</i>	Pomacentridae	R
<i>Tetrapturus angustirostris</i>	Istiophoridae	R	<i>Azurina eupalama</i>	Pomacentridae	RE
<i>Alectis ciliaris</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Azurina intercrusma</i>	Pomacentridae	V
<i>Caranx caballus</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Chromis alta</i>	Pomacentridae	R
<i>Caranx caninus</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Microspathodon bairdii</i>	Pomacentridae	R
<i>Caranx ignobilis</i>	Carangidae	V	<i>Microspathodon dorsalis</i>	Pomacentridae	R
<i>Caranx lugubris</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Nexilosus latifrons</i>	Pomacentridae	R
<i>Caranx melampygus</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Stegastes acapulcoensis</i>	Pomacentridae	R
<i>Caranx sexfasciatus</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Stegastes arcifrons</i>	Pomacentridae	R
<i>Decapterus macarellus</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Stegastes beebei</i>	Pomacentridae	R
<i>Decapterus macrosoma</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Stegastes flavilatus</i>	Pomacentridae	R
<i>Decapterus muroadsi</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Atherinella nesiotis</i>	Atherinopsidae	RE
<i>Elagatis bipinnulata</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Melanorhinus cyanellus</i>	Atherinopsidae	R
<i>Euprepocaranx dorsalis</i>	Carangidae	V	<i>Cololabis adoceta</i>	Scomberesocidae	R
<i>Ferdauia orthogrammus</i>	Carangidae	V	<i>Scomberesox scombroides</i>	Scomberesocidae	R
<i>Gnathanodon speciosus</i>	Carangidae	V	<i>Ablennes hians</i>	Belonidae	R
<i>Naucrates ductor</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Platybelone argalus pterura</i>	Belonidae	R
<i>Oligoplites inornatus</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Strongylura exilis</i>	Belonidae	R
<i>Selar crumenophthalmus</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Tylosurus fodiator</i>	Belonidae	R
<i>Selene peruviana</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Tylosurus pacificus</i>	Belonidae	V
<i>Seriola lalandi</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Euleptorhamphus viridis</i>	Hemiramphidae	R
<i>Seriola peruana</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Hemiramphus saltator</i>	Hemiramphidae	R
<i>Seriola rivoliana</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Hyporhamphus gilli</i>	Hemiramphidae	V
<i>Trachinotus kennedyi</i>	Carangidae	V	<i>Hyporhamphus naos</i>	Hemiramphidae	R
<i>Trachinotus paitensis</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Oxyporhamphus micropterus</i>	Hemiramphidae	R
<i>Trachinotus rhodopus</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Cheilopogon atrisignis</i>	Exocoetidae	R
<i>Trachinotus stilbe</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Cheilopogon dorsomacula</i>	Exocoetidae	R
<i>Trachurus murphyi</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Cheilopogon furcatus</i>	Exocoetidae	R
<i>Uraspis helvola</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Cheilopogon spilonotopterus</i>	Exocoetidae	R
<i>Echeneis naucrates</i>	Echeneidae	R	<i>Cheilopogon xenopterus</i>	Exocoetidae	R
<i>Phtheirichthys lineatus</i>	Echeneidae	R	<i>Cypselurus callopterus</i>	Exocoetidae	R
<i>Remora albescens</i>	Echeneidae	R	<i>Exocoetus monocirrhus</i>	Exocoetidae	R
<i>Remora brachyptera</i>	Echeneidae	R	<i>Exocoetus volitans</i>	Exocoetidae	R
<i>Remora osteochir</i>	Echeneidae	R	<i>Fodiator rostratus</i>	Exocoetidae	R
<i>Remora remora</i>	Echeneidae	R	<i>Hirundichthys marginatus</i>	Exocoetidae	R

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Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Hirundichthys speculiger</i>	Exocoetidae	R	<i>Lutjanus jordani</i>	Lutjanidae	R
<i>Chaenomugil proboscideus</i>	Mugilidae	R	<i>Lutjanus novemfasciatus</i>	Lutjanidae	R
<i>Dajaus monticola</i>	Mugilidae	R	<i>Lutjanus viridis</i>	Lutjanidae	R
<i>Mugil galapagensis</i>	Mugilidae	RE	<i>Pristipomoides zonatus</i>	Lutjanidae	V
<i>Mugil thoburni</i>	Mugilidae	RE	<i>Diapterus brevirostris</i>	Gerreidae	R
<i>Arcos poecilophthalmos</i>	Gobiesocidae	R	<i>Eucinostomus currani</i>	Gerreidae	R
<i>Tomicodon chilensis</i>	Gobiesocidae	R	<i>Eucinostomus dowii</i>	Gerreidae	R
<i>Tomicodon petersii</i>	Gobiesocidae	R	<i>Eucinostomus gracilis</i>	Gerreidae	R
<i>Lepidonectes corallicola</i>	Tripterygiidae	RE	<i>Eugerres lineatus</i>	Gerreidae	R
<i>Cottoclinus canops</i>	Labrisomidae	RE	<i>Gerres simillimus</i>	Gerreidae	R
<i>Dialommus fuscus</i>	Labrisomidae	R	<i>Anisotremus espinozai</i>	Haemulidae	R
<i>Gobioclinus dendriticus</i>	Labrisomidae	R	<i>Anisotremus scapularis</i>	Haemulidae	R
<i>Labrisomus jenkinsi</i>	Labrisomidae	RE	<i>Brachygenys jessiae</i>	Haemulidae	RE
<i>Labrisomus multiporosus</i>	Labrisomidae	R	<i>Haemulon maculicauda</i>	Haemulidae	R
<i>Malacoctenus tetranemus</i>	Labrisomidae	R	<i>Haemulon scudderii</i>	Haemulidae	R
<i>Malacoctenus zonogaster</i>	Labrisomidae	RE	<i>Haemulon sexfasciatum</i>	Haemulidae	R
<i>Starksia galapagensis</i>	Labrisomidae	RE	<i>Microlepidotus lethopristis</i>	Haemulidae	RE
<i>Acanthemblemaria castroi</i>	Chaenopsidae	RE	<i>Orthopristis cantharina</i>	Haemulidae	R
<i>Chaenopsis schmitti</i>	Chaenopsidae	RE	<i>Orthopristis chalcea</i>	Haemulidae	R
<i>Dactyloscopus lacteus</i>	Dactyloscopidae	RE	<i>Orthopristis forbesi</i>	Haemulidae	RE
<i>Gillellus semicinctus</i>	Dactyloscopidae	R	<i>Rhencus macracanthus</i>	Haemulidae	V
<i>Myxodagnus sagitta</i>	Dactyloscopidae	RE	<i>Xenichthys agassizii</i>	Haemulidae	RE
<i>Platygillellus rubellulus</i>	Dactyloscopidae	RE	<i>Xenichthys xanti</i>	Haemulidae	V
<i>Entomacrodus chiostictus</i>	Blenniidae	R	<i>Archosargus pourtalesii</i>	Sparidae	RE
<i>Hypsoblennius brevipinnis</i>	Blenniidae	R	<i>Calamus brachysomus</i>	Sparidae	R
<i>Ophioblennius steindachneri</i>	Blenniidae	R	<i>Calamus taurinus</i>	Sparidae	RE
<i>Plagiotremus azaleus</i>	Blenniidae	R	<i>Corvula macrops</i>	Sciaenidae	R
<i>Scartichthys gigas</i>	Blenniidae	V	<i>Larimus pacificus</i>	Sciaenidae	V
<i>Hemilutjanus macrophthalmos</i>	Malakichthyidae	R	<i>Odontoscion eurymesops</i>	Sciaenidae	R
<i>Heteropriacanthus carolinus</i>	Priacanthidae	R	<i>Pareques perissa</i>	Sciaenidae	RE
<i>Pristigenys serrula</i>	Priacanthidae	R	<i>Umbrina galapagorum</i>	Sciaenidae	RE
<i>Malacanthus brevirostris</i>	Malacanthidae	R	<i>Alphestes immaculatus</i>	Epinephelidae	R
<i>Caulolatilus affinis</i>	Latilidae	R	<i>Cephalopholis colonus</i>	Epinephelidae	R
<i>Caulolatilus princeps</i>	Latilidae	R	<i>Cephalopholis panamensis</i>	Epinephelidae	R
<i>Hoplopagrus guentherii</i>	Lutjanidae	R	<i>Dermatolepis dermatolepis</i>	Epinephelidae	R
<i>Lutjanus aratus</i>	Lutjanidae	R	<i>Epinephelus analogus</i>	Epinephelidae	V
<i>Lutjanus argentiventris</i>	Lutjanidae	R	<i>Epinephelus labriformis</i>	Epinephelidae	R
<i>Lutjanus colorado</i>	Lutjanidae	V	<i>Epinephelus quinquefasciatus</i>	Epinephelidae	V
<i>Lutjanus guttatus</i>	Lutjanidae	R	<i>Hyporthodus cifuentesi</i>	Epinephelidae	R
<i>Lutjanus inermis</i>	Lutjanidae	R	<i>Hyporthodus mystacinus</i>	Epinephelidae	R

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Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Hyporthodus niphobles</i>	Epinephelidae	R	<i>Xyrichtys victori</i>	Labridae	R
<i>Mycteroperca olfax</i>	Epinephelidae	R	<i>Lycodapus australis</i>	Zoarcidae	R
<i>Pseudogramma thaumasia</i>	Grammistidae	R	<i>Melanostigma bathium</i>	Zoarcidae	R
<i>Rypticus bicolor</i>	Grammistidae	R	<i>Pachycara rimae</i>	Zoarcidae	RE
<i>Rypticus nigripinnis</i>	Grammistidae	R	<i>Thermarces cerberus</i>	Zoarcidae	R
<i>Liopropoma fasciatum</i>	Liopropomatidae	R	<i>Ammodytoides gilli</i>	Ammodytidae	R
<i>Liopropoma longilepis</i>	Liopropomatidae	R	<i>Kathetostoma averruncus</i>	Uranoscopidae	V
<i>Cratinus agassizii</i>	Serranidae	R	<i>Bellator farrago</i>	Triglidae	R
<i>Diplectrum eumelum</i>	Serranidae	V	<i>Peristedion crustosum</i>	Triglidae	R
<i>Diplectrum rostrum</i>	Serranidae	R	<i>Prionotus miles</i>	Triglidae	RE
<i>Paralabrax albomaculatus</i>	Serranidae	RE	<i>Prionotus pictus</i>	Triglidae	RE
<i>Serranus aequidens</i>	Serranidae	R	<i>Ectreposebastes imus</i>	Scorpaenidae	R
<i>Serranus psittacinus</i>	Serranidae	R	<i>Idiastion hageyi</i>	Scorpaenidae	RE
<i>Serranus stilbostigma</i>	Serranidae	RE	<i>Phenacoscorpius mccoskeri</i>	Scorpaenidae	RE
<i>Anthias noeli</i>	Anthiidae	R	<i>Pontinus clemensi</i>	Scorpaenidae	R
<i>Hemanthias peruanus</i>	Anthiidae	V	<i>Pontinus furcirhinus</i>	Scorpaenidae	R
<i>Pronotogrammus multifasciatus</i>	Anthiidae	R	<i>Pontinus sierra</i>	Scorpaenidae	R
<i>Bodianus darwini</i>	Labridae	R	<i>Scorpaena cocosensis</i>	Scorpaenidae	R
<i>Bodianus diplotaenia</i>	Labridae	R	<i>Scorpaena histrio</i>	Scorpaenidae	R
<i>Bodianus eclancheri</i>	Labridae	R	<i>Scorpaena mystes</i>	Scorpaenidae	R
<i>Calotomus carolinus</i>	Labridae-Scarinae	V	<i>Scorpaena wellingtoni</i>	Scorpaenidae	RE
<i>Decodon melasma</i>	Labridae	R	<i>Scorpaenodes rubrivinctus</i>	Scorpaenidae	R
<i>Halichoeres adustus</i>	Labridae	V	<i>Scorpaenodes xyris</i>	Scorpaenidae	R
<i>Halichoeres chierchiai</i>	Labridae	R	<i>Sebastolobus altivelis</i>	Scorpaenidae	R
<i>Halichoeres dispilus</i>	Labridae	R	<i>Taenianotus triacanthus</i>	Scorpaenidae	V
<i>Halichoeres malpelo</i>	Labridae	R	<i>Trachyscorpia osheri</i>	Scorpaenidae	R
<i>Halichoeres nicholsi</i>	Labridae	R	<i>Psychrolutes sio</i>	Psychrolutidae	R
<i>Halichoeres notospilus</i>	Labridae	R	<i>Paraliparis darwini</i>	Liparidae	RE
<i>Iniistius pavo</i>	Labridae	R	<i>Paraliparis galapagosensis</i>	Liparidae	RE
<i>Nicholsina denticulata</i>	Labridae-Scarinae	R	<i>Kuhlia mugil</i>	Kuhliidae	R
<i>Novaculichthys taeniourus</i>	Labridae	R	<i>Oplegnathus insignis</i>	Oplegnathidae	R
<i>Sagittalarva inornata</i>	Labridae	R	<i>Kyphosus cinerascens</i>	Kyphosidae	V
<i>Scarus compressus</i>	Labridae-Scarinae	R	<i>Kyphosus elegans</i>	Kyphosidae	R
<i>Scarus ghobban</i>	Labridae-Scarinae	R	<i>Kyphosus ocyurus</i>	Kyphosidae	R
<i>Scarus perrico</i>	Labridae-Scarinae	R	<i>Kyphosus sectatrix</i>	Kyphosidae	R
<i>Scarus rubroviolaceus</i>	Labridae-Scarinae	R	<i>Kyphosus vaigiensis</i>	Kyphosidae	R
<i>Stethojulis bandanensis</i>	Labridae	R	<i>Girella freminwillii</i>	Girellidae	RE
<i>Thalassoma grammaticum</i>	Labridae	R	<i>Cirrhitichthys oxycephalus</i>	Cirrhitidae	R
<i>Thalassoma lucasanum</i>	Labridae	R	<i>Cirrhitus rivulatus</i>	Cirrhitidae	R
<i>Thalassoma purpureum</i>	Labridae	R	<i>Oxycirrhites typus</i>	Cirrhitidae	R

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Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Epigonus macrops</i>	Epigonidae	R	<i>Chaunacops coloratus</i>	Chaunacidae	R
<i>Howella pammelas</i>	Howellidae	R	<i>Melanocetus murrayi</i>	Melanocetidae	R
<i>Lobotes pacifica</i>	Lobotidae	V	<i>Chaenophryne draco</i>	Oneirodidae	R
<i>Holacanthus passer</i>	Pomacanthidae	R	<i>Dolopichthys allector</i>	Oneirodidae	R
<i>Pomacanthus zonipectus</i>	Pomacanthidae	V	<i>Microlophichthys microlophus</i>	Oneirodidae	R
<i>Chaetodon auriga</i>	Chaetodontidae	V	<i>Pentherichthys atratus</i>	Oneirodidae	R
<i>Chaetodon humeralis</i>	Chaetodontidae	R	<i>Cryptopsaras couesii</i>	Ceratiidae	R
<i>Chaetodon kleinii</i>	Chaetodontidae	V	<i>Gigantactis vanhoeffeni</i>	Gigantactinidae	R
<i>Chaetodon lunula</i>	Chaetodontidae	V	<i>Borophryne apogon</i>	Linophryniidae	R
<i>Chaetodon meyeri</i>	Chaetodontidae	V	<i>Masturus lanceolatus</i>	Molidae	R
<i>Chaetodon punctatofasciatus</i>	Chaetodontidae	V	<i>Mola alexandrini</i>	Molidae	R
<i>Chaetodon unimaculatus</i>	Chaetodontidae	V	<i>Chilomycterus reticulatus</i>	Diodontidae	R
<i>Forcipiger flavissimus</i>	Chaetodontidae	R	<i>Cylichthys spilostylus</i>	Diodontidae	V
<i>Johrandallia nigrirostris</i>	Chaetodontidae	R	<i>Diodon holacanthus</i>	Diodontidae	R
<i>Prognathodes carlhubbsi</i>	Chaetodontidae	R	<i>Diodon hystrix</i>	Diodontidae	R
<i>Luvarus imperialis</i>	Luvaridae	R	<i>Arothron hispidus</i>	Tetraodontidae	R
<i>Zanclus cornutus</i>	Zanclidae	R	<i>Arothron meleagris</i>	Tetraodontidae	R
<i>Acanthurus leucocheilus</i>	Acanthuridae	V	<i>Arothron nigropunctatus</i>	Tetraodontidae	V
<i>Acanthurus mata</i>	Acanthuridae	V	<i>Canthigaster amboinensis</i>	Tetraodontidae	V
<i>Acanthurus nigricans</i>	Acanthuridae	R	<i>Canthigaster janthinoptera</i>	Tetraodontidae	V
<i>Acanthurus olivaceus</i>	Acanthuridae	V	<i>Canthigaster punctatissima</i>	Tetraodontidae	R
<i>Acanthurus triostegus</i>	Acanthuridae	V	<i>Canthigaster valentini</i>	Tetraodontidae	V
<i>Acanthurus xanthopterus</i>	Acanthuridae	R	<i>Lagocephalus lagocephalus</i>	Tetraodontidae	R
<i>Ctenochaetus marginatus</i>	Acanthuridae	R	<i>Sphoeroides angusticeps</i>	Tetraodontidae	R
<i>Naso annulatus</i>	Acanthuridae	V	<i>Sphoeroides annulatus</i>	Tetraodontidae	R
<i>Naso brevirostris</i>	Acanthuridae	V	<i>Sphoeroides lobatus</i>	Tetraodontidae	R
<i>Naso hexacanthus</i>	Acanthuridae	R	<i>Lactoria diaphana</i>	Ostraciidae	V
<i>Naso vlamingii</i>	Acanthuridae	V	<i>Ostracion meleagris</i>	Ostraciidae	R
<i>Prionurus laticlavus</i>	Acanthuridae	R	<i>Aluterus monoceros</i>	Monacanthidae	R
<i>Lophiodes spilurus</i>	Lophiidae	R	<i>Aluterus scriptus</i>	Monacanthidae	R
<i>Dibranchius cracens</i>	Ogcocephalidae	RE	<i>Cantherhines dumerilii</i>	Monacanthidae	V
<i>Dibranchius discors</i>	Ogcocephalidae	RE	<i>Balistes polylepis</i>	Balistidae	R
<i>Dibranchius erinaceus</i>	Ogcocephalidae	R	<i>Canthidermis maculata</i>	Balistidae	R
<i>Dibranchius hystrix</i>	Ogcocephalidae	R	<i>Melichthys niger</i>	Balistidae	R
<i>Halieutopsis tumifrons</i>	Ogcocephalidae	RE	<i>Melichthys vidua</i>	Balistidae	R
<i>Ogcocephalus darwini</i>	Ogcocephalidae	R	<i>Pseudobalistes naufragium</i>	Balistidae	R
<i>Abantennarius sanguineus</i>	Antennariidae	R	<i>Sufflamen verres</i>	Balistidae	R
<i>Antennarius commerson</i>	Antennariidae	V	<i>Xanthichthys caeruleolineatus</i>	Balistidae	V
<i>Antennatus strigatus</i>	Antennariidae	R	<i>Xanthichthys mento</i>	Balistidae	V
<i>Fowlerichthys avalonis</i>	Antennariidae	R			

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Fishes of the Galapagos Archipelago
(719 spp. in family alphabetical order)

Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Acanthurus leucocheilus</i>	Acanthuridae	V	<i>Guentherus altivela</i>	Ateleopodidae	R
<i>Acanthurus mata</i>	Acanthuridae	V	<i>Atherinella nesiotis</i>	Atherinopsidae	RE
<i>Acanthurus nigricans</i>	Acanthuridae	R	<i>Melanorhinus cyanellus</i>	Atherinopsidae	R
<i>Acanthurus olivaceus</i>	Acanthuridae	V	<i>Aulopus chirichignoae</i>	Aulopidae	R
<i>Acanthurus triostegus</i>	Acanthuridae	V	<i>Aulostomus chinensis</i>	Aulostomidae	R
<i>Acanthurus xanthopterus</i>	Acanthuridae	R	<i>Balistes polylepis</i>	Balistidae	R
<i>Ctenochaetus marginatus</i>	Acanthuridae	R	<i>Canthidermis maculata</i>	Balistidae	R
<i>Naso annulatus</i>	Acanthuridae	V	<i>Melichthys niger</i>	Balistidae	R
<i>Naso brevirostris</i>	Acanthuridae	V	<i>Melichthys vidua</i>	Balistidae	R
<i>Naso hexacanthus</i>	Acanthuridae	R	<i>Pseudobalistes naufragium</i>	Balistidae	R
<i>Naso vlamingii</i>	Acanthuridae	V	<i>Sufflamen verres</i>	Balistidae	R
<i>Prionurus laticlavus</i>	Acanthuridae	R	<i>Xanthichthys caeruleolineatus</i>	Balistidae	V
<i>Trinectes fonsecensis</i>	Achiridae	V	<i>Xanthichthys mento</i>	Balistidae	V
<i>Aetobatus ocellatus</i>	Aetobatidae	R	<i>Bathylagoides nigrigenys</i>	Bathylagidae	R
<i>Albula esuncula</i>	Albulidae	V	<i>Bathylagus wesethi</i>	Bathylagidae	R
<i>Bathytroctes macrolepis</i>	Alepocephalidae	R	<i>Leuroglossus stilbius</i>	Bathylagidae	R
<i>Einara macrolepis</i>	Alepocephalidae	R	<i>Ablennes hians</i>	Belonidae	R
<i>Narceus erimelas</i>	Alepocephalidae	R	<i>Platybelone argalus pterura</i>	Belonidae	R
<i>Photostylus pycnopterus</i>	Alepocephalidae	R	<i>Strongylura exilis</i>	Belonidae	R
<i>Alopias pelagicus</i>	Alopiidae	R	<i>Tylosurus fodiator</i>	Belonidae	R
<i>Alopias superciliosus</i>	Alopiidae	R	<i>Tylosurus pacificus</i>	Belonidae	V
<i>Sardinops sagax</i>	Alosidae	R	<i>Entomacrodus chiostictus</i>	Blenniidae	R
<i>Ammodytoides gilli</i>	Ammodytidae	R	<i>Hypsoblennius brevipinnis</i>	Blenniidae	R
<i>Anguilla marmorata</i>	Anguillidae	R	<i>Ophioblennius steindachneri</i>	Blenniidae	R
<i>Anoplogaster cornuta</i>	Anoplogastridae	R	<i>Plagiotremus azaleus</i>	Blenniidae	R
<i>Abantennarius sanguineus</i>	Antennariidae	R	<i>Scartichthys gigas</i>	Blenniidae	V
<i>Antennarius commerson</i>	Antennariidae	V	<i>Bothus leopardinus</i>	Bothidae	R
<i>Antennatus strigatus</i>	Antennariidae	R	<i>Bothus mancus</i>	Bothidae	R
<i>Fowlerichthys avalonis</i>	Antennariidae	R	<i>Monolene maculipinna</i>	Bothidae	V
<i>Anthias noeli</i>	Anthiidae	R	<i>Brama dussumieri</i>	Bramidae	R
<i>Hemanthias peruanus</i>	Anthiidae	V	<i>Brama japonica</i>	Bramidae	V
<i>Pronotogrammus multifasciatus</i>	Anthiidae	R	<i>Taractes rubescens</i>	Bramidae	R
<i>Apogon atradorsatus</i>	Apogonidae	R	<i>Branchiostomus elongatus</i>	Branchiostomatidae	R
<i>Apogon dovii</i>	Apogonidae	R	<i>Bregmaceros bathymaster</i>	Bregmacerotidae	V
<i>Apogon pacificus</i>	Apogonidae	R	<i>Bellottia</i> sp.	Bythitidae	R
<i>Argentina aliciae</i>	Argentinidae	R	<i>Calamopteryx jeb</i>	Bythitidae	RE
<i>Bathyraja abyssicola</i>	Arhynchobatidae	R	<i>Cataetx rubirostris</i>	Bythitidae	R
<i>Bathyraja peruana</i>	Arhynchobatidae	R	<i>Cataetx simus</i>	Bythitidae	R
<i>Bathyraja richardsoni</i>	Arhynchobatidae	R	<i>Diplacanthopoma jordani</i>	Bythitidae	R
<i>Bathyraja spinosissima</i>	Arhynchobatidae	R	<i>Grammonus diagrammus</i>	Bythitidae	R

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Fishes of the Galapagos Archipelago

Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Lucifuga inopinata</i>	Bythitidae	RE	<i>Prionace glauca</i>	Carcharhinidae	R
<i>Petrotyx hopkinsi</i>	Bythitidae	R	<i>Triaenodon obesus</i>	Carcharhinidae	R
<i>Pseudonus acutus</i>	Bythitidae	R	<i>Paracaristius</i> sp.	Caristiidae	R
<i>Thermichthys hollisi</i>	Bythitidae	RE	<i>Seriolaella violacea</i>	Centrolophidae	R
<i>Synchiropus atrilabiatus</i>	Callionymidae	R	<i>Centrophorus squamosus</i>	Centrophoridae	R
<i>Alectis ciliaris</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Centropomus viridis</i>	Centropomidae	R
<i>Caranx caballus</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Cryptopsaras couesii</i>	Ceratiidae	R
<i>Caranx caninus</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Cetomimus gillii</i>	Cetomimidae	R
<i>Caranx ignobilis</i>	Carangidae	V	<i>Acanthemblemaria castroi</i>	Chaenopsidae	RE
<i>Caranx lugubris</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Chaenopsis schmitti</i>	Chaenopsidae	RE
<i>Caranx melampygus</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Chaetodon auriga</i>	Chaetodontidae	V
<i>Caranx sexfasciatus</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Chaetodon humeralis</i>	Chaetodontidae	R
<i>Decapterus macarellus</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Chaetodon kleinii</i>	Chaetodontidae	V
<i>Decapterus macrosoma</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Chaetodon lunula</i>	Chaetodontidae	V
<i>Decapterus muroadsi</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Chaetodon meyeri</i>	Chaetodontidae	V
<i>Elagatis bipinnulata</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Chaetodon punctatofasciatus</i>	Chaetodontidae	V
<i>Eupreopcaranx dorsalis</i>	Carangidae	V	<i>Chaetodon unimaculatus</i>	Chaetodontidae	V
<i>Ferdauia orthogrammus</i>	Carangidae	V	<i>Forcipiger flavissimus</i>	Chaetodontidae	R
<i>Gnathanodon speciosus</i>	Carangidae	V	<i>Johnrandallia nigrirostris</i>	Chaetodontidae	R
<i>Naucrates ductor</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Prognathodes carlhubbsi</i>	Chaetodontidae	R
<i>Oligoplites inornatus</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Chanos chanos</i>	Chanidae	R
<i>Selar crumenophthalmus</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Chaunacops coloratus</i>	Chaunacidae	R
<i>Selene peruviana</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Chiasmodon niger</i>	Chiasmodontidae	R
<i>Seriola lalandi</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Chiasmodon subniger</i>	Chiasmodontidae	R
<i>Seriola peruana</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Hydrolagus alphas</i>	Chimaeridae	RE
<i>Seriola rivoliiana</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Hydrolagus mccooskeri</i>	Chimaeridae	RE
<i>Trachinotus kennedyi</i>	Carangidae	V	<i>Hydrolagus melanophasma</i>	Chimaeridae	R
<i>Trachinotus paitensis</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Hydrolagus</i> n. sp.	Chimaeridae	RE
<i>Trachinotus rhodopus</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Chlopsis bicollaris</i>	Chlopsidae	R
<i>Trachinotus stilbe</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Chlorophthalmus mento</i>	Chlorophthalmidae	R
<i>Trachurus murphyi</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Cirrhitichthys oxycephalus</i>	Cirrhitidae	R
<i>Uraspis helvola</i>	Carangidae	R	<i>Cirrhitus rivulatus</i>	Cirrhitidae	R
<i>Carcharhinus albimarginatus</i>	Carcharhinidae	R	<i>Oxycirrhites typus</i>	Cirrhitidae	R
<i>Carcharhinus altimus</i>	Carcharhinidae	R	<i>Harengula thrissina</i>	Clupeidae	R
<i>Carcharhinus amblyrhynchos</i>	Carcharhinidae	V	<i>Lile stolifera</i>	Clupeidae	R
<i>Carcharhinus falciformis</i>	Carcharhinidae	R	<i>Opisthonema berlangai</i>	Clupeidae	RE
<i>Carcharhinus galapagensis</i>	Carcharhinidae	R	<i>Opisthonema libertate</i>	Clupeidae	R
<i>Carcharhinus limbatus</i>	Carcharhinidae	R	<i>Ariosoma gilberti</i>	Congridae	R
<i>Carcharhinus longimanus</i>	Carcharhinidae	R	<i>Bathycongrus varidens</i>	Congridae	R
<i>Nasolamia velox</i>	Carcharhinidae	R	<i>Heteroconger klausewitzii</i>	Congridae	R

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Fishes of the Galapagos Archipelago

Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Japonoconger proriger</i>	Congridae	R	<i>Anchoa argentivittata</i>	Engraulidae	R
<i>Paraconger californiensis</i>	Congridae	R	<i>Anchoa ischana</i>	Engraulidae	R
<i>Paraconger similis</i>	Congridae	R	<i>Cetengraulis mysticetus</i>	Engraulidae	V
<i>Xenomystax atrarius</i>	Congridae	R	<i>Engraulis ringens</i>	Engraulidae	R
<i>Coryphaena equiselis</i>	Coryphaenidae	R	<i>Epigonus macrops</i>	Epigonidae	R
<i>Coryphaena hippurus</i>	Coryphaenidae	R	<i>Alphestes immaculatus</i>	Epinephelidae	R
<i>Citharichthys darwini</i>	Cyclosettidae	RE	<i>Cephalopholis colonus</i>	Epinephelidae	R
<i>Citharichthys gnathus</i>	Cyclosettidae	R	<i>Cephalopholis panamensis</i>	Epinephelidae	R
<i>Syacium latifrons</i>	Cyclosettidae	V	<i>Dermatolepis dermatolepis</i>	Epinephelidae	R
<i>Syacium maculiferum</i>	Cyclosettidae	V	<i>Epinephelus analogus</i>	Epinephelidae	V
<i>Symphurus atramentatus</i>	Cynoglossidae	R	<i>Epinephelus labriformis</i>	Epinephelidae	R
<i>Symphurus diabolicus</i>	Cynoglossidae	R	<i>Epinephelus quinquefasciatus</i>	Epinephelidae	V
<i>Symphurus varius</i>	Cynoglossidae	R	<i>Hyporthodus cifuentesi</i>	Epinephelidae	R
<i>Dactyloscopus lacteus</i>	Dactyloscopidae	RE	<i>Hyporthodus mystacinus</i>	Epinephelidae	R
<i>Gillellus semicinctus</i>	Dactyloscopidae	R	<i>Hyporthodus niphobles</i>	Epinephelidae	R
<i>Myxodagnus sagitta</i>	Dactyloscopidae	RE	<i>Mycteroperca olfax</i>	Epinephelidae	R
<i>Platygillellus rubellulus</i>	Dactyloscopidae	RE	<i>Centroscyllium nigrum</i>	Etmopteridae	R
<i>Isistius brasiliensis</i>	Dalatiidae	R	<i>Evermannella ahlstromi</i>	Evermannellidae	R
<i>Hypanus dipterurus</i>	Dasyatidae	R	<i>Cheilopogon atrisignis</i>	Exocoetidae	R
<i>Hypanus longus</i>	Dasyatidae	R	<i>Cheilopogon dorsomacula</i>	Exocoetidae	R
<i>Pteroplatytrygon violacea</i>	Dasyatidae	R	<i>Cheilopogon furcatus</i>	Exocoetidae	R
<i>Taeniurops meyeri</i>	Dasyatidae	R	<i>Cheilopogon spilonotopterus</i>	Exocoetidae	R
<i>Ogilbia deroyi</i>	Dinematichthyidae	RE	<i>Cheilopogon xenopterus</i>	Exocoetidae	R
<i>Ogilbia galapagosensis</i>	Dinematichthyidae	RE	<i>Cypselurus callopterus</i>	Exocoetidae	R
<i>Chilomycterus reticulatus</i>	Diodontidae	R	<i>Exocoetus monocirrhus</i>	Exocoetidae	R
<i>Cylichthys spilostylus</i>	Diodontidae	V	<i>Exocoetus volitans</i>	Exocoetidae	R
<i>Diodon holocanthus</i>	Diodontidae	R	<i>Fodiator rostratus</i>	Exocoetidae	R
<i>Diodon hystrix</i>	Diodontidae	R	<i>Hirundichthys marginatus</i>	Exocoetidae	R
<i>Etrumeus acuminatus</i>	Dussumieriidae	R	<i>Hirundichthys speculiger</i>	Exocoetidae	R
<i>Echeneis naucrates</i>	Echeneidae	R	<i>Fistularia commersonii</i>	Fistulariidae	R
<i>Phtheirichthys lineatus</i>	Echeneidae	R	<i>Fistularia corneta</i>	Fistulariidae	V
<i>Remora albescens</i>	Echeneidae	R	<i>Galeocerdo cuvier</i>	Galeocerdonidae	R
<i>Remora brachyptera</i>	Echeneidae	R	<i>Gempylus serpens</i>	Gempylidae	R
<i>Remora osteochir</i>	Echeneidae	R	<i>Lepidocybium flavobrunneum</i>	Gempylidae	R
<i>Remora remora</i>	Echeneidae	R	<i>Nealotus tripes</i>	Gempylidae	R
<i>Echinorhinus cookei</i>	Echinorhinidae	R	<i>Ruvettus pretiosus</i>	Gempylidae	R
<i>Dormitator latifrons</i>	Eleotridae	V	<i>Diapterus brevirostris</i>	Gerreidae	R
<i>Eleotris picta</i>	Eleotridae	V	<i>Eucinostomus currani</i>	Gerreidae	R
<i>Gobiomorus maculatus</i>	Eleotridae	V	<i>Eucinostomus dowii</i>	Gerreidae	R
<i>Elops affinis</i>	Elopidae	V	<i>Eucinostomus gracilis</i>	Gerreidae	R

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Fishes of the Galapagos Archipelago

Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Eugerres lineatus</i>	Gerreidae	R	<i>Orthopristis cantharina</i>	Haemulidae	R
<i>Gerres simillimus</i>	Gerreidae	R	<i>Orthopristis chalcea</i>	Haemulidae	R
<i>Gigantactis vanhoeffeni</i>	Gigantactinidae	R	<i>Orthopristis forbesi</i>	Haemulidae	RE
<i>Girella freminvillii</i>	Girellidae	RE	<i>Rhencus macracanthus</i>	Haemulidae	V
<i>Arcos poecilophthalmos</i>	Gobiesocidae	R	<i>Xenichthys agassizii</i>	Haemulidae	RE
<i>Tomicodon chilensis</i>	Gobiesocidae	R	<i>Xenichthys xanti</i>	Haemulidae	V
<i>Tomicodon petersii</i>	Gobiesocidae	R	<i>Halosaurus attenuatus</i>	Halosauridae	R
<i>Bathygobius lineatus</i>	Gobiidae	R	<i>Euleptorhamphus viridis</i>	Hemiramphidae	R
<i>Chriolepis tagus</i>	Gobiidae	RE	<i>Hemiramphus saltator</i>	Hemiramphidae	R
<i>Clarkichthys bilineatus</i>	Gobiidae	R	<i>Hyporhamphus gilli</i>	Hemiramphidae	V
<i>Coryphopterus urospilus</i>	Gobiidae	R	<i>Hyporhamphus naos</i>	Hemiramphidae	R
<i>Eleotrica cableae</i>	Gobiidae	RE	<i>Oxyporhamphus micropterus</i>	Hemiramphidae	R
<i>Evorthodus minutus</i>	Gobiidae	V	<i>Heterodontus quoyi</i>	Heterodontidae	R
<i>Lythrypnus gilberti</i>	Gobiidae	RE	<i>Hexanchus griseus</i>	Hexanchidae	R
<i>Lythrypnus rhizophora</i>	Gobiidae	R	<i>Notorynchus cepedianus</i>	Hexanchidae	R
<i>Microdesmus dipus</i>	Gobiidae	V	<i>Myripristis berndti</i>	Holocentridae	R
<i>Schindleria praematura</i>	Gobiidae	R	<i>Myripristis leiognathus</i>	Holocentridae	R
<i>Tigrigobius nesiotes</i>	Gobiidae	R	<i>Neoniphon suborbitalis</i>	Holocentridae	R
<i>Cyclothone acclinidens</i>	Gonostomatidae	R	<i>Howella pammelas</i>	Howellidae	R
<i>Cyclothone alba</i>	Gonostomatidae	R	<i>Bathypterois atricolor</i>	Ipnopidae	R
<i>Cyclothone atraria</i>	Gonostomatidae	R	<i>Bathypterois pectinatus</i>	Ipnopidae	R
<i>Cyclothone braueri</i>	Gonostomatidae	R	<i>Ipnops agassizii</i>	Ipnopidae	R
<i>Cyclothone microdon</i>	Gonostomatidae	R	<i>Istiompax indica</i>	Istiophoridae	R
<i>Cyclothone obscura</i>	Gonostomatidae	R	<i>Istiophorus platypterus</i>	Istiophoridae	R
<i>Cyclothone pallida</i>	Gonostomatidae	R	<i>Kajikia audax</i>	Istiophoridae	R
<i>Cyclothone pseudopallida</i>	Gonostomatidae	R	<i>Makaira nigricans</i>	Istiophoridae	R
<i>Cyclothone signata</i>	Gonostomatidae	R	<i>Tetrapturus angustirostris</i>	Istiophoridae	R
<i>Diplophos proximus</i>	Gonostomatidae	R	<i>Kuhlia mugil</i>	Kuhliidae	R
<i>Sigmops elongatus</i>	Gonostomatidae	R	<i>Kyphosus cinerascens</i>	Kyphosidae	V
<i>Pseudogramma thaumasia</i>	Grammistidae	R	<i>Kyphosus elegans</i>	Kyphosidae	R
<i>Rypticus bicolor</i>	Grammistidae	R	<i>Kyphosus ocyurus</i>	Kyphosidae	R
<i>Rypticus nigripinnis</i>	Grammistidae	R	<i>Kyphosus sectatrix</i>	Kyphosidae	R
<i>Gurgesiella furvescens</i>	Gurgesiellidae	R	<i>Kyphosus vaigiensis</i>	Kyphosidae	R
<i>Anisotremus espinozai</i>	Haemulidae	R	<i>Bodianus darwini</i>	Labridae	R
<i>Anisotremus scapularis</i>	Haemulidae	R	<i>Bodianus diplotaenia</i>	Labridae	R
<i>Brachygenys jessiae</i>	Haemulidae	RE	<i>Bodianus eclancheri</i>	Labridae	R
<i>Haemulon maculicauda</i>	Haemulidae	R	<i>Calotomus carolinus</i>	Labridae-Scarinae	V
<i>Haemulon scudderii</i>	Haemulidae	R	<i>Decodon melasma</i>	Labridae	R
<i>Haemulon sexfasciatum</i>	Haemulidae	R	<i>Halichoeres adustus</i>	Labridae	V
<i>Microlepidotus lethopristis</i>	Haemulidae	RE	<i>Halichoeres chierchiae</i>	Labridae	R

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Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Halichoeres dispilus</i>	Labridae	R	<i>Lutjanus guttatus</i>	Lutjanidae	R
<i>Halichoeres malpelo</i>	Labridae	R	<i>Lutjanus inermis</i>	Lutjanidae	R
<i>Halichoeres nicholsi</i>	Labridae	R	<i>Lutjanus jordani</i>	Lutjanidae	R
<i>Halichoeres notospilus</i>	Labridae	R	<i>Lutjanus novemfasciatus</i>	Lutjanidae	R
<i>Iniistius pavo</i>	Labridae	R	<i>Lutjanus viridis</i>	Lutjanidae	R
<i>Nicholsina denticulata</i>	Labridae-Scarinae	R	<i>Pristipomoides zonatus</i>	Lutjanidae	V
<i>Novaculichthys taeniourus</i>	Labridae	R	<i>Luvarus imperialis</i>	Luvaridae	R
<i>Sagittalarva inornata</i>	Labridae	R	<i>Coelorinchus canus</i>	Macrouridae	R
<i>Scarus compressus</i>	Labridae-Scarinae	R	<i>Coryphaenoides anguliceps</i>	Macrouridae	R
<i>Scarus ghobban</i>	Labridae-Scarinae	R	<i>Coryphaenoides armatus</i>	Macrouridae	R
<i>Scarus perrico</i>	Labridae-Scarinae	R	<i>Coryphaenoides boops</i>	Macrouridae	R
<i>Scarus rubroviolaceus</i>	Labridae-Scarinae	R	<i>Coryphaenoides bucephalus</i>	Macrouridae	R
<i>Stethojulis bandanensis</i>	Labridae	R	<i>Coryphaenoides bulbiceps</i>	Macrouridae	R
<i>Thalassoma grammaticum</i>	Labridae	R	<i>Coryphaenoides delsolari</i>	Macrouridae	R
<i>Thalassoma lucasanum</i>	Labridae	R	<i>Coryphaenoides gypsochilus</i>	Macrouridae	RE
<i>Thalassoma purpureum</i>	Labridae	R	<i>Coryphaenoides myersi</i>	Macrouridae	RE
<i>Xyrichtys victori</i>	Labridae	R	<i>Mataeocephalus tenuicauda</i>	Macrouridae	R
<i>Cottoclinus canops</i>	Labrisomidae	RE	<i>Nezumia convergens</i>	Macrouridae	R
<i>Dialommus fuscus</i>	Labrisomidae	R	<i>Nezumia loricata</i>	Macrouridae	RE
<i>Gobioclinus dendriticus</i>	Labrisomidae	R	<i>Nezumia parini</i>	Macrouridae	R
<i>Labrisomus jenkinsi</i>	Labrisomidae	RE	<i>Nezumia stelgidolepis</i>	Macrouridae	R
<i>Labrisomus multiporosus</i>	Labrisomidae	R	<i>Nezumia ventralis</i>	Macrouridae	RE
<i>Malacoctenus tetranemus</i>	Labrisomidae	R	<i>Malacanthus brevirostris</i>	Malacanthidae	R
<i>Malacoctenus zonogaster</i>	Labrisomidae	RE	<i>Hemilutjanus macrophthalmos</i>	Malakichthyidae	R
<i>Starksia galapagensis</i>	Labrisomidae	RE	<i>Melamphaes laeviceps</i>	Melamphaidae	R
<i>Carcharodon carcharias</i>	Lamnidae	V	<i>Melamphaes spinifer</i>	Melamphaidae	R
<i>Isurus oxyrinchus</i>	Lamnidae	R	<i>Poromitra cf. crassiceps</i>	Melamphaidae	R
<i>Caulolatilus affinis</i>	Latilidae	R	<i>Poromitra frontosa</i>	Melamphaidae	R
<i>Caulolatilus princeps</i>	Latilidae	R	<i>Poromitra jucunda</i>	Melamphaidae	R
<i>Borophryne apogon</i>	Linophryidae	R	<i>Poromitra nigrofulva</i>	Melamphaidae	R
<i>Liopropoma fasciatum</i>	Liopropomatidae	R	<i>Poromitra oscitans</i>	Melamphaidae	R
<i>Liopropoma longilepis</i>	Liopropomatidae	R	<i>Scopeloberyx opisthopterus</i>	Melamphaidae	R
<i>Paraliparis darwini</i>	Liparidae	RE	<i>Scopeloberyx robustus</i>	Melamphaidae	R
<i>Paraliparis galapagosensis</i>	Liparidae	RE	<i>Scopelogadus bispinosus</i>	Melamphaidae	R
<i>Lobotes pacifica</i>	Lobotidae	V	<i>Melanocetus murrayi</i>	Melanocetidae	R
<i>Lophiodes spilurus</i>	Lophiidae	R	<i>Mobula birostris</i>	Mobulidae	R
<i>Hoplopagrus guentherii</i>	Lutjanidae	R	<i>Mobula mobular</i>	Mobulidae	R
<i>Lutjanus aratus</i>	Lutjanidae	R	<i>Mobula munkiana</i>	Mobulidae	R
<i>Lutjanus argentiventris</i>	Lutjanidae	R	<i>Mobula tarapacana</i>	Mobulidae	R
<i>Lutjanus colorado</i>	Lutjanidae	V	<i>Mobula thurstoni</i>	Mobulidae	R

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Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Masturus lanceolatus</i>	Molidae	R	<i>Bolinichthys longipes</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Mola alexandrini</i>	Molidae	R	<i>Centrobranchus andreae</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Aluterus monoceros</i>	Monacanthidae	R	<i>Centrobranchus nigroocellatus</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Aluterus scriptus</i>	Monacanthidae	R	<i>Dasyscopelus asper</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Cantherhines dumerilii</i>	Monacanthidae	V	<i>Diaphus fulgens</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Antimora rostrata</i>	Moridae	R	<i>Diaphus mollis</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Gadella filifer</i>	Moridae	R	<i>Diaphus pacificus</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Gadella thysthlon</i>	Moridae	RE	<i>Diaphus parri</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Laemonema gracillipes</i>	Moridae	R	<i>Diaphus rafinesquii</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Physiculus nematopus</i>	Moridae	R	<i>Diaphus termophilus</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Chaenomugil proboscideus</i>	Mugilidae	R	<i>Diaphus theta</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Dajaus monticola</i>	Mugilidae	R	<i>Diogenichthys laternatus</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Mugil galapagensis</i>	Mugilidae	RE	<i>Gonichthys tenuiculus</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Mugil thoburni</i>	Mugilidae	RE	<i>Gonichthys venetus</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Mulloidichthys dentatus</i>	Mullidae	R	<i>Hygophum reinhardtii</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Pseudupeneus grandisquamis</i>	Mullidae	R	<i>Lampadena luminosa</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Anarchias galapagensis</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Lampanyctus crypticus</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Echidna nebulosa</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Lampanyctus hubbsi</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Echidna nocturna</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Lampanyctus idostigma</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Enchelycore lichenosa</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Lampanyctus macropterus</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Enchelycore octaviana</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Lampanyctus nobilis</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Gymnomuraena zebra</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Lampanyctus omostigma</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Gymnothorax angusticeps</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Lampanyctus parvicauda</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Gymnothorax buroensis</i>	Muraenidae	V	<i>Lampanyctus ritteri</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Gymnothorax castaneus</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Lampanyctus tenuiformis</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Gymnothorax dovii</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Loweina rara</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Gymnothorax flavimarginatus</i>	Muraenidae	V	<i>Myctophum affine</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Gymnothorax javanicus</i>	Muraenidae	V	<i>Myctophum aurolaternatum</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Gymnothorax meleagris</i>	Muraenidae	V	<i>Myctophum brachygnathum</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Gymnothorax panamensis</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Myctophum nitidulum</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Gymnothorax pictus</i>	Muraenidae	V	<i>Notolychnus valdiviae</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Gymnothorax porphyreus</i>	Muraenidae	V	<i>Notoscopelus elongatus</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Gymnothorax undulatus</i>	Muraenidae	V	<i>Notoscopelus resplendens</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Muraena argus</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Protomyctophum sp.</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Muraena clepsydra</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Symbolophorus evermanni</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Muraena lentiginosa</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Symbolophorus reversus</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Scuticaria tigrina</i>	Muraenidae	V	<i>Triphoturus mexicanus</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Uropterygius macrocephalus</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Triphoturus nigricans</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Uropterygius polystictus</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Triphoturus oculous</i>	Myctophidae	R
<i>Uropterygius versutus</i>	Muraenidae	R	<i>Aetomylaeus asperrimus</i>	Myliobatidae	R

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Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Myliobatis peruviana</i>	Myliobatidae	R	<i>Myrichthys xysturus</i>	Ophichthidae	R
<i>Myroconger nigrodentatus</i>	Myrocongridae	R	<i>Ophichthus arneutes</i>	Ophichthidae	RE
<i>Eptatretus bobwisneri</i>	Myxinidae	RE	<i>Ophichthus rugifer</i>	Ophichthidae	R
<i>Eptatretus goslinei</i>	Myxinidae	RE	<i>Paraetharchus opercularis</i>	Ophichthidae	R
<i>Eptatretus grouseri</i>	Myxinidae	RE	<i>Phaenomonas pinnata</i>	Ophichthidae	R
<i>Eptatretus mccoskeri</i>	Myxinidae	RE	<i>Quassiremus evionthas</i>	Ophichthidae	R
<i>Myxine greggi</i>	Myxinidae	RE	<i>Scytalichthys miurus</i>	Ophichthidae	V
<i>Myxine martinii</i>	Myxinidae	RE	<i>Bathyonus caudalis</i>	Ophidiidae	R
<i>Myxine phantasma</i>	Myxinidae	RE	<i>Brotula ordwayi</i>	Ophidiidae	R
<i>Rubicundus lakeside</i>	Myxinidae	RE	<i>Dicrolene nigra</i>	Ophidiidae	R
<i>Avocettina infans</i>	Nemichthyidae	R	<i>Echiodon exsilium</i>	Ophidiidae	R
<i>Nemichthys scolopaceus</i>	Nemichthyidae	R	<i>Encheliophis vermicularis</i>	Ophidiidae	R
<i>Scopelogys tristis</i>	Neoscopelidae	R	<i>Eretmichthys pinnatus</i>	Ophidiidae	R
<i>Facciolella equatorialis</i>	Nettastomatidae	R	<i>Lamprogrammus niger</i>	Ophidiidae	R
<i>Cubiceps baxteri</i>	Nomeidae	R	<i>Lepophidium pardale</i>	Ophidiidae	R
<i>Cubiceps pauciradiatus</i>	Nomeidae	R	<i>Monomitopus malispinosus</i>	Ophidiidae	R
<i>Nomeus gronovii</i>	Nomeidae	R	<i>Monomitopus torvus</i>	Ophidiidae	R
<i>Psenes arafurensis</i>	Nomeidae	R	<i>Ophidion galapagensis</i>	Ophidiidae	R
<i>Psenes cyanophrys</i>	Nomeidae	R	<i>Otophidium indefatigabile</i>	Ophidiidae	R
<i>Psenes pellucidus</i>	Nomeidae	R	<i>Porogadus promelas</i>	Ophidiidae	R
<i>Psenes sio</i>	Nomeidae	R	<i>Spectrunculus crassus</i>	Ophidiidae	R
<i>Notacanthus spinosus</i>	Notacanthidae	R	<i>Bathylychnops</i> sp.	Opisthoproctidae	R
<i>Scopelosaurus harryi</i>	Notosudidae	R	<i>Dolichopteryx pseudolongipes</i>	Opisthoproctidae	R
<i>Scopelosaurus hubbsi</i>	Notosudidae	R	<i>Opistognathus galapagensis</i>	Opistognathidae	R
<i>Odontaspis ferox</i>	Odontaspidae	R	<i>Oplegnathus insignis</i>	Oplegnathidae	R
<i>Dibranchius cracens</i>	Ogcocephalidae	RE	<i>Lactoria diaphana</i>	Ostraciidae	V
<i>Dibranchius discors</i>	Ogcocephalidae	RE	<i>Ostracion meleagris</i>	Ostraciidae	R
<i>Dibranchius erinaceus</i>	Ogcocephalidae	R	<i>Lestidiops pacificus</i>	Paralepididae	R
<i>Dibranchius hystrix</i>	Ogcocephalidae	R	<i>Lestidium bigelowi</i>	Paralepididae	R
<i>Halieutopsis tumifrons</i>	Ogcocephalidae	RE	<i>Stemonosudis macrura</i>	Paralepididae	R
<i>Ogcocephalus darwini</i>	Ogcocephalidae	R	<i>Hippoglossina bollmani</i>	Paralichthyidae	R
<i>Chaenophryne draco</i>	Oneirodidae	R	<i>Paralichthys woolmani</i>	Paralichthyidae	R
<i>Dolopichthys allector</i>	Oneirodidae	R	<i>Apristurus kampa</i>	Pentanchidae	R
<i>Microlophichthys microlophus</i>	Oneirodidae	R	<i>Apristurus</i> n. sp.	Pentanchidae	RE
<i>Pentherichthys atratus</i>	Oneirodidae	R	<i>Ichthyococcus irregularis</i>	Phosichthyidae	R
<i>Apterichthys equatorialis</i>	Ophichthidae	R	<i>Vinciguerria lucetius</i>	Phosichthyidae	R
<i>Bascanichthys bascanoides</i>	Ophichthidae	R	<i>Vinciguerria nimbaria</i>	Phosichthyidae	R
<i>Callechelys galapagensis</i>	Ophichthidae	RE	<i>Vinciguerria poweriae</i>	Phosichthyidae	R
<i>Herpetoichthys fossatus</i>	Ophichthidae	R	<i>Yarella argenteola</i>	Phosichthyidae	R
<i>Ichthyapus selachops</i>	Ophichthidae	R	<i>Holtbyrnia latifrons</i>	Platyroctidae	R

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Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Maulisia isaacsi</i>	Platytroctidae	R	<i>Euthynnus lineatus</i>	Scombridae	R
<i>Platytroctes apus</i>	Platytroctidae	R	<i>Katsuwonus pelamis</i>	Scombridae	R
<i>Sagamichthys abei</i>	Platytroctidae	R	<i>Sarda orientalis</i>	Scombridae	R
<i>Polydactylus approximans</i>	Polynemidae	V	<i>Scomber japonicus</i>	Scombridae	R
<i>Holacanthus passer</i>	Pomacanthidae	R	<i>Scomberomorus sierra</i>	Scombridae	R
<i>Pomacanthus zonipectus</i>	Pomacanthidae	V	<i>Thunnus albacares</i>	Scombridae	R
<i>Abudefduf concolor</i>	Pomacentridae	R	<i>Thunnus obesus</i>	Scombridae	R
<i>Abudefduf troschelii</i>	Pomacentridae	R	<i>Rosenblattichthys volucris</i>	Scopelarchidae	R
<i>Azurina atrilobata</i>	Pomacentridae	R	<i>Scopelarchoides nicholsi</i>	Scopelarchidae	R
<i>Azurina eupalama</i>	Pomacentridae	RE	<i>Scopelarchus guentheri</i>	Scopelarchidae	R
<i>Azurina intercrusma</i>	Pomacentridae	V	<i>Ectreposebastes imus</i>	Scorpaenidae	R
<i>Chromis alta</i>	Pomacentridae	R	<i>Idiastion hageyi</i>	Scorpaenidae	RE
<i>Microspathodon bairdii</i>	Pomacentridae	R	<i>Phenacoscorpius mccoskeri</i>	Scorpaenidae	RE
<i>Microspathodon dorsalis</i>	Pomacentridae	R	<i>Pontinus clemensi</i>	Scorpaenidae	R
<i>Nexilosus latifrons</i>	Pomacentridae	R	<i>Pontinus furcirhinus</i>	Scorpaenidae	R
<i>Stegastes acapulcoensis</i>	Pomacentridae	R	<i>Pontinus sierra</i>	Scorpaenidae	R
<i>Stegastes arcifrons</i>	Pomacentridae	R	<i>Scorpaena cocosensis</i>	Scorpaenidae	R
<i>Stegastes beebei</i>	Pomacentridae	R	<i>Scorpaena histrio</i>	Scorpaenidae	R
<i>Stegastes flavilatus</i>	Pomacentridae	R	<i>Scorpaena mystes</i>	Scorpaenidae	R
<i>Styracura pacifica</i>	Potamotrygonidae	R	<i>Scorpaena wellingtoni</i>	Scorpaenidae	RE
<i>Heteropriacanthus carolinus</i>	Priacanthidae	R	<i>Scorpaenodes rubrivinctus</i>	Scorpaenidae	R
<i>Pristigenys serrula</i>	Priacanthidae	R	<i>Scorpaenodes xyris</i>	Scorpaenidae	R
<i>Psychrolutes sio</i>	Psychrolutidae	R	<i>Sebastolobus altivelis</i>	Scorpaenidae	R
<i>Rajella eisenhardti</i>	Rajidae	RE	<i>Taenianotus triacanthus</i>	Scorpaenidae	V
<i>Rostroraja velezi</i>	Rajidae	R	<i>Trachyscorpia osheri</i>	Scorpaenidae	R
<i>Regalecus russellii</i>	Regalacidae	R	<i>Bythaelurus giddingsi</i>	Scyliorhinidae	RE
<i>Rhincodon typus</i>	Rhincodontidae	R	<i>Galeus n. sp.</i>	Scyliorhinidae	RE
<i>Pseudobatos planiceps</i>	Rhinobatidae	R	<i>Cratinus agassizii</i>	Serranidae	R
<i>Rhinoptera steindachneri</i>	Rhinopteridae	R	<i>Diplectrum eumelum</i>	Serranidae	V
<i>Rondeletia loricata</i>	Rondeletiidae	R	<i>Diplectrum rostrum</i>	Serranidae	R
<i>Corvula macrops</i>	Sciaenidae	R	<i>Paralabrax albomaculatus</i>	Serranidae	RE
<i>Larimus pacificus</i>	Sciaenidae	V	<i>Serranus aequidens</i>	Serranidae	R
<i>Odontoscion eurymesops</i>	Sciaenidae	R	<i>Serranus psittacinus</i>	Serranidae	R
<i>Pareques perissa</i>	Sciaenidae	RE	<i>Serranus stilbostigma</i>	Serranidae	RE
<i>Umbrina galapagorum</i>	Sciaenidae	RE	<i>Serrivomer sector</i>	Serrivomeridae	R
<i>Cololabis adoceta</i>	Scomberesocidae	R	<i>Aseraggodes herrei</i>	Soleidae	R
<i>Scomberesox scombroides</i>	Scomberesocidae	R	<i>Archosargus pourtalesii</i>	Sparidae	RE
<i>Acanthocybium solandri</i>	Scombridae	R	<i>Calamus brachysomus</i>	Sparidae	R
<i>Auxis rochei</i>	Scombridae	R	<i>Calamus taurinus</i>	Sparidae	RE
<i>Auxis thazard</i>	Scombridae	R	<i>Sphyraena barracuda</i>	Sphyraenidae	V

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Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Sphyraena idiaestes</i>	Sphyraenidae	R	<i>Synodus lacertinus</i>	Synodontidae	R
<i>Sphyraena stellata</i>	Sphyraenidae	R	<i>Synodus scituliceps</i>	Synodontidae	R
<i>Sphyrna lewini</i>	Sphyrnidae	R	<i>Synodus sechurae</i>	Synodontidae	R
<i>Sphyrna zygaena</i>	Sphyrnidae	R	<i>Tetragonurus atlanticus</i>	Tetragonuridae	R
<i>Argyropelecus aculeatus</i>	Sternoptychidae	R	<i>Arothron hispidus</i>	Tetraodontidae	R
<i>Argyropelecus affinis</i>	Sternoptychidae	R	<i>Arothron meleagris</i>	Tetraodontidae	R
<i>Argyropelecus lychnus</i>	Sternoptychidae	R	<i>Arothron nigropunctatus</i>	Tetraodontidae	V
<i>Argyropelecus olfersii</i>	Sternoptychidae	R	<i>Canthigaster amboinensis</i>	Tetraodontidae	V
<i>Argyropelecus sladeni</i>	Sternoptychidae	R	<i>Canthigaster janthinoptera</i>	Tetraodontidae	V
<i>Danaphos oculatus</i>	Sternoptychidae	R	<i>Canthigaster punctatissima</i>	Tetraodontidae	R
<i>Maurollicus australis</i>	Sternoptychidae	R	<i>Canthigaster valentini</i>	Tetraodontidae	V
<i>Sternoptyx diaphana</i>	Sternoptychidae	R	<i>Lagocephalus lagocephalus</i>	Tetraodontidae	R
<i>Sternoptyx obscura</i>	Sternoptychidae	R	<i>Sphoeroides angusticeps</i>	Tetraodontidae	R
<i>Sternoptyx pseudobscura</i>	Sternoptychidae	R	<i>Sphoeroides annulatus</i>	Tetraodontidae	R
<i>Valencienellus tripunctulatus</i>	Sternoptychidae	R	<i>Sphoeroides lobatus</i>	Tetraodontidae	R
<i>Astronesthes cyanea</i>	Stomiidae	R	<i>Tetronarce tremens</i>	Torpedinidae	R
<i>Astronesthes galapagensis</i>	Stomiidae	R	<i>Hoplostethus pacificus</i>	Trachichthyidae	RE
<i>Astronesthes gibbsi</i>	Stomiidae	R	<i>Desmodema polystictum</i>	Trachipteridae	R
<i>Astronesthes indica</i>	Stomiidae	R	<i>Zu cristatus</i>	Trachipteridae	R
<i>Astronesthes lampara</i>	Stomiidae	R	<i>Trachyrincus helolepis</i>	Trachyrincidae	R
<i>Bathophilus filifer</i>	Stomiidae	R	<i>Mustelus albipinnis</i>	Triakidae	R
<i>Borostomias elucens</i>	Stomiidae	R	<i>Mustelus mento</i>	Triakidae	R
<i>Borostomias panamensis</i>	Stomiidae	R	<i>Triakis maculata</i>	Triakidae	R
<i>Chauliodus barbatus</i>	Stomiidae	R	<i>Aphanopus capricornis</i>	Trichiuridae	R
<i>Chauliodus sloani</i>	Stomiidae	R	<i>Benthodesmus tenuis</i>	Trichiuridae	R
<i>Idiacanthus antrostomus</i>	Stomiidae	R	<i>Lepidopus manis</i>	Trichiuridae	R
<i>Malacosteus niger</i>	Stomiidae	R	<i>Trichiurus nitens</i>	Trichiuridae	R
<i>Photonectes margarita</i>	Stomiidae	R	<i>Bellator farrago</i>	Triglidae	R
<i>Stomias atriventer</i>	Stomiidae	R	<i>Peristedion crustosum</i>	Triglidae	R
<i>Stomias colubrinus</i>	Stomiidae	R	<i>Prionotus miles</i>	Triglidae	RE
<i>Stomias danae</i>	Stomiidae	R	<i>Prionotus pictus</i>	Triglidae	RE
<i>Thysanactis dentex</i>	Stomiidae	R	<i>Lepidonectes corallicola</i>	Tripterygiidae	RE
<i>Peprilus medius</i>	Stromateidae	R	<i>Kathetostoma avertuncus</i>	Uranoscopidae	V
<i>Stylephorus chordatus</i>	Stylephoridae	R	<i>Xiphias gladius</i>	Xiphiidae	R
<i>Ilyophis arx</i>	Synaphobranchidae	R	<i>Zanclus cornutus</i>	Zanclidae	R
<i>Ilyophis brunneus</i>	Synaphobranchidae	R	<i>Lycodapus australis</i>	Zoarcidae	R
<i>Bryx veleronis</i>	Syngnathidae	R	<i>Melanostigma bathium</i>	Zoarcidae	R
<i>Cosmocampus coccineus</i>	Syngnathidae	R	<i>Pachycara rimae</i>	Zoarcidae	RE
<i>Doryrhamphus melanopleura</i>	Syngnathidae	R	<i>Thermarces cerberus</i>	Zoarcidae	R
<i>Hippocampus ingens</i>	Syngnathidae	R			

TABLE 3

Fishes of the Galapagos Archipelago
endemic species (69 spp.)

Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Atherinella nesiotis</i>	ATHERINOPSIDAE	RE	<i>Eptatretus mccoskeri</i>	MYXINIDAE	RE
<i>Calamopteryx jeb</i>	BYTHITIDAE	RE	<i>Myxine greggi</i>	MYXINIDAE	RE
<i>Lucifuga inopinata</i>	BYTHITIDAE	RE	<i>Myxine martinii</i>	MYXINIDAE	RE
<i>Thermichthys hollisi</i>	BYTHITIDAE	RE	<i>Myxine phantasma</i>	MYXINIDAE	RE
<i>Acanthemblemaria castroi</i>	CHAENOPSIDAE	RE	<i>Rubicundus lakeside</i>	MYXINIDAE	RE
<i>Chaenopsis schmitti</i>	CHAENOPSIDAE	RE	<i>Dibranchus cracens</i>	OGCOEPHALIDAE	RE
<i>Hydrolagus alphas</i>	CHIMAERIDAE	RE	<i>Dibranchus discors</i>	OGCOEPHALIDAE	RE
<i>Hydrolagus mccoskeri</i>	CHIMAERIDAE	RE	<i>Halieutopsis tumifrons</i>	OGCOEPHALIDAE	RE
<i>Hydrolagus</i> n. sp.	CHIMAERIDAE	RE	<i>Callechelys galapagensis</i>	OPHICHTHIDAE	RE
<i>Opisthonema berlangai</i>	CLUPEIDAE	RE	<i>Ophichthus arneutes</i>	OPHICHTHIDAE	RE
<i>Citharichthys darwini</i>	CYCLOPSETTA	RE	<i>Apristurus</i> n. sp.	PENTANCHIDAE	RE
<i>Dactyloscopus lacteus</i>	DACTYLOSCOPIDAE	RE	<i>Azurina eupalama</i>	POMACENTRIDAE	RE
<i>Myxodagnus sagitta</i>	DACTYLOSCOPIDAE	RE	<i>Rajella eisenhardti</i>	RAJIDAE	RE
<i>Platygillellus rubellulus</i>	DACTYLOSCOPIDAE	RE	<i>Pareques perissa</i>	SCIAENIDAE	RE
<i>Ogilbia deroyi</i>	DINEMATICHTHYIDAE	RE	<i>Umbrina galapagorum</i>	SCIAENIDAE	RE
<i>Ogilbia galapagosensis</i>	DINEMATICHTHYIDAE	RE	<i>Idiastion hageyi</i>	SCORPAENIDAE	RE
<i>Girella freminivillii</i>	GIRELLIDAE	RE	<i>Phenacoscorpius mccoskeri</i>	SCORPAENIDAE	RE
<i>Chriolepis tagus</i>	GOBIIDAE	RE	<i>Scorpaena wellingtoni</i>	SCORPAENIDAE	RE
<i>Eleotrica cableae</i>	GOBIIDAE	RE	<i>Bythaelurus giddingsi</i>	SCYLORHINIDAE	RE
<i>Lythrypnus gilberti</i>	GOBIIDAE	RE	<i>Galeus</i> n. sp.	SCYLORHINIDAE	RE
<i>Brachygenys jessiae</i>	HAEMULIDAE	RE	<i>Paralabrax albomaculatus</i>	SERRANIDAE	RE
<i>Microlepidotus lethopristis</i>	HAEMULIDAE	RE	<i>Serranus stilbostigma</i>	SERRANIDAE	RE
<i>Orthopristis forbesi</i>	HAEMULIDAE	RE	<i>Archosargus pourtalesii</i>	SPARIDAE	RE
<i>Xenichthys agassizii</i>	HAEMULIDAE	RE	<i>Calamus taurinus</i>	SPARIDAE	RE
<i>Cottoclinus canops</i>	LABRISOMIDAE	RE	<i>Hoplostethus pacificus</i>	TRACHICHTHYIDAE	RE
<i>Labrisomus jenkinsi</i>	LABRISOMIDAE	RE	<i>Prionotus miles</i>	TRIGLIDAE	RE
<i>Malacoctenus zonogaster</i>	LABRISOMIDAE	RE	<i>Prionotus pictus</i>	TRIGLIDAE	RE
<i>Starksia galapagensis</i>	LABRISOMIDAE	RE	<i>Lepidonectes corallicola</i>	TRIPTERYGIIDAE	RE
<i>Paraliparis darwini</i>	LIPARIDAE	RE	<i>Pachycara rimae</i>	ZOARCIDAE	RE
<i>Paraliparis galapagosensis</i>	LIPARIDAE	RE			
<i>Coryphaenoides gypsochilus</i>	MACROURIDAE	RE			
<i>Coryphaenoides myersi</i>	MACROURIDAE	RE			
<i>Nezumia loricata</i>	MACROURIDAE	RE			
<i>Nezumia ventralis</i>	MACROURIDAE	RE			
<i>Gadella thysthlon</i>	MORIDAE	RE			
<i>Mugil galapagensis</i>	MUGILIDAE	RE			
<i>Mugil thoburni</i>	MUGILIDAE	RE			
<i>Eptatretus bobwisneri</i>	MYXINIDAE	RE			
<i>Eptatretus goslinei</i>	MYXINIDAE	RE			
<i>Eptatretus grouseri</i>	MYXINIDAE	RE			

TABLE 4

Fishes of the Galapagos Archipelago
shallow shorefish vagrants (64 spp.) & other vagrants (13 spp.)

Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Acanthurus leucocheilus</i>	ACANTHURIDAE	V	<i>Lutjanus colorado</i>	LUTJANIDAE	V
<i>Acanthurus mata</i>	ACANTHURIDAE	V	<i>Pristipomoides zonatus</i>	LUTJANIDAE	V
<i>Acanthurus olivaceus</i>	ACANTHURIDAE	V	<i>Cantherhines dumerilii</i>	MONACANTHIDAE	V
<i>Acanthurus triostegus</i>	ACANTHURIDAE	V	<i>Gymnothorax buroensis</i>	MURAENIDAE	V
<i>Naso annulatus</i>	ACANTHURIDAE	V	<i>Gymnothorax flavimarginatus</i>	MURAENIDAE	V
<i>Naso brevirostris</i>	ACANTHURIDAE	V	<i>Gymnothorax javanicus</i>	MURAENIDAE	V
<i>Naso vlamingii</i>	ACANTHURIDAE	V	<i>Gymnothorax meleagris</i>	MURAENIDAE	V
<i>Trinectes fonsecensis</i>	ACHIRIDAE	V	<i>Gymnothorax pictus</i>	MURAENIDAE	V
<i>Albula esuncula</i>	ALBULIDAE	V	<i>Gymnothorax porphyreus</i>	MURAENIDAE	V
<i>Antennarius commerson</i>	ANTENNARIIDAE	V	<i>Gymnothorax undulatus</i>	MURAENIDAE	V
<i>Xanthichthys caeruleolineatus</i>	BALISTIDAE	V	<i>Scuticaria tigrina</i>	MURAENIDAE	V
<i>Xanthichthys mento</i>	BALISTIDAE	V	<i>Scytalichthys miurus</i>	OPHICHTHIDAE	V
<i>Tylosurus pacificus</i>	BELONIDAE	V	<i>Polydactylus approximans</i>	POLYNEMIDAE	V
<i>Scartichthys gigas</i>	BLENNIIDAE	V	<i>Pomacanthus zonipectus</i>	POMACANTHIDAE	V
<i>Chaetodon auriga</i>	CHAETODONTIDAE	V	<i>Azurina intercrusma</i>	POMACENTRIDAE	V
<i>Chaetodon kleinii</i>	CHAETODONTIDAE	V	<i>Larimus pacificus</i>	SCIAENIDAE	V
<i>Chaetodon lunula</i>	CHAETODONTIDAE	V	<i>Taenianotus triacanthus</i>	SCORPAENIDAE	V
<i>Chaetodon meyeri</i>	CHAETODONTIDAE	V	<i>Diplectrum eumelum</i>	SERRANIDAE	V
<i>Chaetodon punctatofasciatus</i>	CHAETODONTIDAE	V	<i>Sphyræna barracuda</i>	SPHYRAENIDAE	V
<i>Chaetodon unimaculatus</i>	CHAETODONTIDAE	V	<i>Arothron nigropunctatus</i>	TETRAODONTIDAE	V
<i>Syacium latifrons</i>	CYCLOPSETTIDAE	V	<i>Canthigaster amboinensis</i>	TETRAODONTIDAE	V
<i>Syacium maculiferum</i>	CYCLOPSETTIDAE	V	<i>Canthigaster janthinoptera</i>	TETRAODONTIDAE	V
<i>Cylichthys spilostylus</i>	DIODONTIDAE	V	<i>Canthigaster valentini</i>	TETRAODONTIDAE	V
<i>Dormitator latifrons</i>	ELEOTRIDAE	V	<i>Kathetostoma averruncus</i>	URANOSCOPIDAE	V
<i>Eleotris picta</i>	ELEOTRIDAE	V			
<i>Gobiomorus maculatus</i>	ELEOTRIDAE	V	OTHER VAGRANTS (13) = deep x2, nr/off pelagic x5/x6		
<i>Elops affinis</i>	ELOPIDAE	V			
<i>Cetengraulis mysticetus</i>	ENGRAULIDAE	V	<i>Hemanthias peruanus</i>	ANTHIADIDAE	V
<i>Epinephelus analogus</i>	EPINEPHELIDAE	V	<i>Monolene maculipinna</i>	BOTHIDAE	V
<i>Epinephelus quinquefasciatus</i>	EPINEPHELIDAE	V	<i>Brama japonica</i>	BRAMIDAE	V
<i>Fistularia corneta</i>	FISTULARIIDAE	V	<i>Bregmaceros bathymaster</i>	BREGMACEROTIDAE	V
<i>Evorthodus minutus</i>	GOBIIDAE	V	<i>Caranx ignobilis</i>	CARANGIDAE	V
<i>Microdesmus dipus</i>	GOBIIDAE	V	<i>Euprepocaranx dorsalis</i>	CARANGIDAE	V
<i>Rhencus macracanthus</i>	HAEMULIDAE	V	<i>Ferdauia orthogrammus</i>	CARANGIDAE	V
<i>Xenichthys xanti</i>	HAEMULIDAE	V	<i>Gnathanodon speciosus</i>	CARANGIDAE	V
<i>Hyporhamphus gilli</i>	HEMIRAMPHIDAE	V	<i>Trachinotus kennedyi</i>	CARANGIDAE	V
<i>Kyphosus cinerascens</i>	KYPHOSIDAE	V	<i>Carcharhinus amblyrhynchos</i>	CARCHARHINIDAE	V
<i>Calotomus carolinus</i>	LABRIDAE-SCARINAE	V	<i>Carcharodon carcharias</i>	LAMNIDAE	V
<i>Halichoeres adustus</i>	LABRIDAE	V	<i>Aetomylaeus asperrimus</i>	MYLIOBATIDAE	V
<i>Lobotes pacifica</i>	LOBOTIDAE	V	<i>Lactoria diaphana</i>	OSTRACIIDAE	V

TABLE 5 (p. 1)

Fishes of the Galapagos Archipelago
shallow shorefish residents (266 spp.)

Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Acanthurus nigricans</i>	ACANTHURIDAE	R	<i>Chaetodon humeralis</i>	CHAETODONTIDAE	R
<i>Acanthurus xanthopterus</i>	ACANTHURIDAE	R	<i>Forcipiger flavissimus</i>	CHAETODONTIDAE	R
<i>Ctenochaetus marginatus</i>	ACANTHURIDAE	R	<i>Johnrandallia nigrirostris</i>	CHAETODONTIDAE	R
<i>Naso hexacanthus</i>	ACANTHURIDAE	R	<i>Prognathodes carlhubbsi</i>	CHAETODONTIDAE	R
<i>Prionurus laticlavus</i>	ACANTHURIDAE	R	<i>Chanos chanos</i>	CHANIDAE	R
<i>Sardinops sagax</i>	ALOSIDAE	R	<i>Cirrhitichthys oxycephalus</i>	CIRRHITIDAE	R
<i>Ammodytoides gilli</i>	AMMODYTIDAE	R	<i>Cirrhitus rivulatus</i>	CIRRHITIDAE	R
<i>Anguilla marmorata</i>	ANGUILLIDAE	R	<i>Oxycirrhites typus</i>	CIRRHITIDAE	R
<i>Abantennarius sanguineus</i>	ANTENNARIIDAE	R	<i>Harengula thrissina</i>	CLUPEIDAE	R
<i>Antennatus strigatus</i>	ANTENNARIIDAE	R	<i>Lile stolifera</i>	CLUPEIDAE	R
<i>Fowlerichthys avalonis</i>	ANTENNARIIDAE	R	<i>Opisthonema berlangai</i>	CLUPEIDAE	RE
<i>Apogon atradorsatus</i>	APOGONIDAE	R	<i>Opisthonema libertate</i>	CLUPEIDAE	R
<i>Apogon dovii</i>	APOGONIDAE	R	<i>Heteroconger klausewitzi</i>	CONGRIDAE	R
<i>Apogon pacificus</i>	APOGONIDAE	R	<i>Citharichthys darwini</i>	CYCLOPSETTIDAE	RE
<i>Atherinella nesiotis</i>	ATHERINOPSIDAE	RE	<i>Citharichthys gnathus</i>	CYCLOPSETTIDAE	R
<i>Melanorhinus cyanellus</i>	ATHERINOPSIDAE	R	<i>Symphurus atramentatus</i>	CYNOGLOSSIDAE	R
<i>Aulostomus chinensis</i>	AULOSTOMIDAE	R	<i>Dactyloscopus lacteus</i>	DACTYLOSCOPIDAE	RE
<i>Balistes polylepis</i>	BALISTIDAE	R	<i>Gillellus semicinctus</i>	DACTYLOSCOPIDAE	R
<i>Canthidermis maculata</i>	BALISTIDAE	R	<i>Myxodagnus sagitta</i>	DACTYLOSCOPIDAE	RE
<i>Melichthys niger</i>	BALISTIDAE	R	<i>Platygillellus rubellulus</i>	DACTYLOSCOPIDAE	RE
<i>Melichthys vidua</i>	BALISTIDAE	R	<i>Hypanus dipterurus</i>	DASYATIDAE	R
<i>Pseudobalistes naufragium</i>	BALISTIDAE	R	<i>Hypanus longus</i>	DASYATIDAE	R
<i>Sufflamen verres</i>	BALISTIDAE	R	<i>Ogilbia deroyi</i>	DINEMATICHTHYIDAE	RE
<i>Platybelone argalus pterura</i>	BELONIDAE	R	<i>Ogilbia galapagosensis</i>	DINEMATICHTHYIDAE	RE
<i>Strongylura exilis</i>	BELONIDAE	R	<i>Chilomycterus reticulatus</i>	DIODONTIDAE	R
<i>Tylosurus fodiator</i>	BELONIDAE	R	<i>Diodon holocanthus</i>	DIODONTIDAE	R
<i>Entomacrodus chiostictus</i>	BLENNIIDAE	R	<i>Diodon hystrix</i>	DIODONTIDAE	R
<i>Hypsoblennius brevipinnis</i>	BLENNIIDAE	R	<i>Etrumeus acuminatus</i>	DUSSUMIERIIDAE	R
<i>Ophioblennius steindachneri</i>	BLENNIIDAE	R	<i>Anchoa argentivittata</i>	ENGRAULIDAE	R
<i>Plagiotremus azaleus</i>	BLENNIIDAE	R	<i>Anchoa ischana</i>	ENGRAULIDAE	R
<i>Bothus leopardinus</i>	BOTHIDAE	R	<i>Engraulis ringens</i>	ENGRAULIDAE	R
<i>Bothus mancus</i>	BOTHIDAE	R	<i>Alphestes immaculatus</i>	EPINEPHELIDAE	R
<i>Branchiostomus elongatus</i>	BRANCHIOSTOMATIDAE	R	<i>Cephalopholis colonus</i>	EPINEPHELIDAE	R
<i>Calamopteryx jeb</i>	BYTHITIDAE	RE	<i>Cephalopholis panamensis</i>	EPINEPHELIDAE	R
<i>Grammonus diagrammus</i>	BYTHITIDAE	R	<i>Dermatolepis dermatolepis</i>	EPINEPHELIDAE	R
<i>Petrotyx hopkinsi</i>	BYTHITIDAE	R	<i>Epinephelus labriformis</i>	EPINEPHELIDAE	R
<i>Synchiropus atrilabiatu</i>	CALLIONYMIDAE	R	<i>Hyporthodus mystacinus</i>	EPINEPHELIDAE	R
<i>Centropomus viridis</i>	CENTROPOMIDAE	R	<i>Hyporthodus niphobles</i>	EPINEPHELIDAE	R
<i>Acanthemblemaria castroi</i>	CHAENOPSIDAE	RE	<i>Mycteroperca olfax</i>	EPINEPHELIDAE	R
<i>Chaenopsis schmitti</i>	CHAENOPSIDAE	RE	<i>Fistularia commersonii</i>	FISTULARIIDAE	R

TABLE 5 (p. 2)

Fishes of the Galapagos Archipelago
shallow shorefish residents (266 spp.)

Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Diapterus brevirostris</i>	GERREIDAE	R	<i>Kyphosus elegans</i>	KYPHOSIDAE	R
<i>Eucinostomus currani</i>	GERREIDAE	R	<i>Kyphosus ocyurus</i>	KYPHOSIDAE	R
<i>Eucinostomus dowii</i>	GERREIDAE	R	<i>Kyphosus sectatrix</i>	KYPHOSIDAE	R
<i>Eucinostomus gracilis</i>	GERREIDAE	R	<i>Kyphosus vaigiensis</i>	KYPHOSIDAE	R
<i>Eugerres lineatus</i>	GERREIDAE	R	<i>Bodianus darwini</i>	LABRIDAE	R
<i>Gerres simillimus</i>	GERREIDAE	R	<i>Bodianus diplotaenia</i>	LABRIDAE	R
<i>Girella freminwillii</i>	GIRELLIDAE	RE	<i>Bodianus eclancheri</i>	LABRIDAE	R
<i>Arcos poecilophthalmos</i>	GOBIESOCIDAE	R	<i>Halichoeres chierchiae</i>	LABRIDAE	R
<i>Tomocodon chilensis</i>	GOBIESOCIDAE	R	<i>Halichoeres dispilus</i>	LABRIDAE	R
<i>Tomocodon petersii</i>	GOBIESOCIDAE	R	<i>Halichoeres malpelo</i>	LABRIDAE	R
<i>Bathygobius lineatus</i>	GOBIIDAE	R	<i>Halichoeres nicholsi</i>	LABRIDAE	R
<i>Chriolepis tagus</i>	GOBIIDAE	RE	<i>Halichoeres notospilus</i>	LABRIDAE	R
<i>Clarkichthys bilineatus</i>	GOBIIDAE	R	<i>Iniistius pavo</i>	LABRIDAE	R
<i>Coryphopterus urospilus</i>	GOBIIDAE	R	<i>Nicholsina denticulata</i>	LABRIDAE-SCARINAE	R
<i>Eleotrica cableae</i>	GOBIIDAE	RE	<i>Novaculichthys taeniourus</i>	LABRIDAE	R
<i>Lythrypnus gilberti</i>	GOBIIDAE	RE	<i>Scarus compressus</i>	LABRIDAE-SCARINAE	R
<i>Lythrypnus rhizophora</i>	GOBIIDAE	R	<i>Scarus ghobban</i>	LABRIDAE-SCARINAE	R
<i>Schindleria praematura</i>	GOBIIDAE	R	<i>Scarus perrico</i>	LABRIDAE-SCARINAE	R
<i>Tigrigobius nesiotes</i>	GOBIIDAE	R	<i>Scarus rubroviolaceus</i>	LABRIDAE-SCARINAE	R
<i>Pseudogramma thaumasia</i>	GRAMMISTIDAE	R	<i>Stethojulis bandanensis</i>	LABRIDAE	R
<i>Rypticus bicolor</i>	GRAMMISTIDAE	R	<i>Thalassoma grammaticum</i>	LABRIDAE	R
<i>Rypticus nigripinnis</i>	GRAMMISTIDAE	R	<i>Thalassoma lucasanum</i>	LABRIDAE	R
<i>Anisotremus espinozai</i>	HAEMULIDAE	R	<i>Thalassoma purpureum</i>	LABRIDAE	R
<i>Anisotremus scapularis</i>	HAEMULIDAE	R	<i>Xyrichtys victori</i>	LABRIDAE	R
<i>Brachygenys jessiae</i>	HAEMULIDAE	RE	<i>Cottoclinus canops</i>	LABRISOMIDAE	RE
<i>Haemulon maculicauda</i>	HAEMULIDAE	R	<i>Dialommus fuscus</i>	LABRISOMIDAE	R
<i>Haemulon scudderii</i>	HAEMULIDAE	R	<i>Gobioclinus dendriticus</i>	LABRISOMIDAE	R
<i>Haemulon sexfasciatum</i>	HAEMULIDAE	R	<i>Labrisomus jenkinsi</i>	LABRISOMIDAE	RE
<i>Microlepidotus lethopristis</i>	HAEMULIDAE	RE	<i>Labrisomus multiporosus</i>	LABRISOMIDAE	R
<i>Orthopristis cantharina</i>	HAEMULIDAE	R	<i>Malacoctenus tetranemus</i>	LABRISOMIDAE	R
<i>Orthopristis chalcea</i>	HAEMULIDAE	R	<i>Malacoctenus zonogaster</i>	LABRISOMIDAE	RE
<i>Orthopristis forbesi</i>	HAEMULIDAE	RE	<i>Starksia galapagensis</i>	LABRISOMIDAE	RE
<i>Xenichthys agassizii</i>	HAEMULIDAE	RE	<i>Caulolatilus affinis</i>	LATILIDAE	R
<i>Hemiramphus saltator</i>	HEMIRAMPHIDAE	R	<i>Caulolatilus princeps</i>	LATILIDAE	R
<i>Hyporhamphus naos</i>	HEMIRAMPHIDAE	R	<i>Liopropoma fasciatum</i>	LIOPROPOMATIDAE	R
<i>Heterodontus quoyi</i>	HETERODONTIDAE	R	<i>Hoplopagrus guentherii</i>	LUTJANIDAE	R
<i>Myripristis berndti</i>	HOLOCENTRIDAE	R	<i>Lutjanus aratus</i>	LUTJANIDAE	R
<i>Myripristis leiognathus</i>	HOLOCENTRIDAE	R	<i>Lutjanus argentiventris</i>	LUTJANIDAE	R
<i>Neoniphon suborbitalis</i>	HOLOCENTRIDAE	R	<i>Lutjanus guttatus</i>	LUTJANIDAE	R
<i>Kuhlia mugil</i>	KUHLIIDAE	R	<i>Lutjanus inermis</i>	LUTJANIDAE	R

TABLE 5 (p. 3)

Fishes of the Galapagos Archipelago
shallow shorefish residents (266 spp.)

Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Lutjanus jordani</i>	LUTJANIDAE	R	<i>Quassiremus evionthas</i>	OPHICHTHIDAE	R
<i>Lutjanus novemfasciatus</i>	LUTJANIDAE	R	<i>Brotula ordwayi</i>	OPHIDIIDAE	R
<i>Lutjanus viridis</i>	LUTJANIDAE	R	<i>Echiodon exsilium</i>	OPHIDIIDAE	R
<i>Malacanthus brevirostris</i>	MALACANTHIDAE	R	<i>Encheliophis vermicularis</i>	OPHIDIIDAE	R
<i>Hemilutjanus macrophthalmos</i>	MALAKICHTHYIDAE	R	<i>Lepophidium pardale</i>	OPHIDIIDAE	R
<i>Aluterus monoceros</i>	MONACANTHIDAE	R	<i>Ophidion galapagensis</i>	OPHIDIIDAE	R
<i>Aluterus scriptus</i>	MONACANTHIDAE	R	<i>Otophidium indefatigabile</i>	OPHIDIIDAE	R
<i>Chaenomugil proboscideus</i>	MUGILIDAE	R	<i>Opistognathus galapagensis</i>	OPISTOGNATHIDAE	R
<i>Dajaus monticola</i>	MUGILIDAE	R	<i>Oplegnathus insignis</i>	OPLEGNATHIDAE	R
<i>Mugil galapagensis</i>	MUGILIDAE	RE	<i>Ostracion meleagris</i>	OSTRACIIDAE	R
<i>Mugil thoburni</i>	MUGILIDAE	RE	<i>Hippoglossina bollmani</i>	PARALICHTHYIDAE	R
<i>Mulloidichthys dentatus</i>	MULLIDAE	R	<i>Paralichthys woolmani</i>	PARALICHTHYIDAE	R
<i>Pseudupeneus grandisquamis</i>	MULLIDAE	R	<i>Holacanthus passer</i>	POMACANTHIDAE	R
<i>Anarchias galapagensis</i>	MURAENIDAE	R	<i>Abudefduf concolor</i>	POMACENTRIDAE	R
<i>Echidna nebulosa</i>	MURAENIDAE	R	<i>Abudefduf troschelii</i>	POMACENTRIDAE	R
<i>Echidna nocturna</i>	MURAENIDAE	R	<i>Azurina atrilobata</i>	POMACENTRIDAE	R
<i>Enchelycore lichenosa</i>	MURAENIDAE	R	<i>Azurina eupalama</i>	POMACENTRIDAE	RE
<i>Enchelycore octaviana</i>	MURAENIDAE	R	<i>Chromis alta</i>	POMACENTRIDAE	R
<i>Gymnomuraena zebra</i>	MURAENIDAE	R	<i>Microspathodon bairdii</i>	POMACENTRIDAE	R
<i>Gymnothorax angusticeps</i>	MURAENIDAE	R	<i>Microspathodon dorsalis</i>	POMACENTRIDAE	R
<i>Gymnothorax castaneus</i>	MURAENIDAE	R	<i>Nexilosus latifrons</i>	POMACENTRIDAE	R
<i>Gymnothorax dovii</i>	MURAENIDAE	R	<i>Stegastes acapulcoensis</i>	POMACENTRIDAE	R
<i>Gymnothorax panamensis</i>	MURAENIDAE	R	<i>Stegastes arcifrons</i>	POMACENTRIDAE	R
<i>Muraena argus</i>	MURAENIDAE	R	<i>Stegastes beebei</i>	POMACENTRIDAE	R
<i>Muraena clepsydra</i>	MURAENIDAE	R	<i>Stegastes flavilatus</i>	POMACENTRIDAE	R
<i>Muraena lentiginosa</i>	MURAENIDAE	R	<i>Styracura pacifica</i>	POTAMOTRYGONIDAE	R
<i>Uropterygius macrocephalus</i>	MURAENIDAE	R	<i>Heteropriacanthus carolinus</i>	PRIACANTHIDAE	R
<i>Uropterygius polystictus</i>	MURAENIDAE	R	<i>Pristigenys serrula</i>	PRIACANTHIDAE	R
<i>Uropterygius versutus</i>	MURAENIDAE	R	<i>Rostroraja velezi</i>	RAJIDAE	R
<i>Ogcocephalus darwini</i>	OGCOCEPHALIDAE	R	<i>Pseudobatos planiceps</i>	RHINOBATIDAE	R
<i>Apterichthys equatorialis</i>	OPHICHTHIDAE	R	<i>Corvula macrops</i>	SCIAENIDAE	R
<i>Bascanichthys bascanoides</i>	OPHICHTHIDAE	R	<i>Odontoscion eurymesops</i>	SCIAENIDAE	R
<i>Callechelys galapagensis</i>	OPHICHTHIDAE	RE	<i>Pareques perissa</i>	SCIAENIDAE	RE
<i>Herpetoichthys fossatus</i>	OPHICHTHIDAE	R	<i>Umbrina galapagorum</i>	SCIAENIDAE	RE
<i>Ichthyapus selachops</i>	OPHICHTHIDAE	R	<i>Scorpaena histrio</i>	SCORPAENIDAE	R
<i>Myrichthys xysturus</i>	OPHICHTHIDAE	R	<i>Scorpaena mystes</i>	SCORPAENIDAE	R
<i>Ophichthus arneutes</i>	OPHICHTHIDAE	RE	<i>Scorpaena wellingtoni</i>	SCORPAENIDAE	RE
<i>Ophichthus rugifer</i>	OPHICHTHIDAE	R	<i>Scorpaenodes xyris</i>	SCORPAENIDAE	R
<i>Paraetharchus opercularis</i>	OPHICHTHIDAE	R	<i>Cratinus agassizii</i>	SERRANIDAE	R
<i>Phaenomonas pinnata</i>	OPHICHTHIDAE	R	<i>Diplectrum rostrum</i>	SERRANIDAE	R

TABLE 5 (p. 4)

Fishes of the Galapagos Archipelago

shallow shorefish residents (266 spp.)

nearshore pelagics (26 spp.)

Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Paralabrax albomaculatus</i>	SERRANIDAE	RE	<i>Alectis ciliaris</i>	CARANGIDAE	R
<i>Serranus psittacinus</i>	SERRANIDAE	R	<i>Caranx caballus</i>	CARANGIDAE	R
<i>Aseraggodes herrei</i>	SOLEIDAE	R	<i>Caranx caninus</i>	CARANGIDAE	R
<i>Archosargus pourtalesii</i>	SPARIDAE	RE	<i>Caranx ignobilis</i>	CARANGIDAE	V
<i>Calamus brachysomus</i>	SPARIDAE	R	<i>Caranx lugubris</i>	CARANGIDAE	R
<i>Calamus taurinus</i>	SPARIDAE	RE	<i>Caranx melampygus</i>	CARANGIDAE	R
<i>Sphyraena idiaestes</i>	SPHYRAENIDAE	R	<i>Caranx sexfasciatus</i>	CARANGIDAE	R
<i>Sphyraena stellata</i>	SPHYRAENIDAE	R	<i>Decapterus macarellus</i>	CARANGIDAE	R
<i>Bryx veleronis</i>	SYNGNATHIDAE	R	<i>Decapterus macrosoma</i>	CARANGIDAE	R
<i>Cosmocampus coccineus</i>	SYNGNATHIDAE	R	<i>Decapterus muroadsi</i>	CARANGIDAE	R
<i>Doryrhamphus melanopleura</i>	SYNGNATHIDAE	R	<i>Elagatis bipinnulata</i>	CARANGIDAE	R
<i>Hippocampus ingens</i>	SYNGNATHIDAE	R	<i>Euprepcaranx dorsalis</i>	CARANGIDAE	V
<i>Synodus lacertinus</i>	SYNODONTIDAE	R	<i>Ferdauia orthogrammus</i>	CARANGIDAE	V
<i>Synodus scituliceps</i>	SYNODONTIDAE	R	<i>Gnathanodon speciosus</i>	CARANGIDAE	V
<i>Synodus sechurae</i>	SYNODONTIDAE	R	<i>Oligoplites inornatus</i>	CARANGIDAE	R
<i>Arothron hispidus</i>	TETRAODONTIDAE	R	<i>Selar crumenophthalmus</i>	CARANGIDAE	R
<i>Arothron meleagris</i>	TETRAODONTIDAE	R	<i>Selene peruviana</i>	CARANGIDAE	R
<i>Canthigaster punctatissima</i>	TETRAODONTIDAE	R	<i>Seriola lalandi</i>	CARANGIDAE	R
<i>Sphoeroides angusticeps</i>	TETRAODONTIDAE	R	<i>Seriola peruana</i>	CARANGIDAE	R
<i>Sphoeroides annulatus</i>	TETRAODONTIDAE	R	<i>Seriola rivoliana</i>	CARANGIDAE	R
<i>Sphoeroides lobatus</i>	TETRAODONTIDAE	R	<i>Trachinotus kennedyi</i>	CARANGIDAE	V
<i>Tetronarce tremens</i>	TORPEDINIDAE	R	<i>Trachinotus paitensis</i>	CARANGIDAE	R
<i>Prionotus miles</i>	TRIGLIDAE	RE	<i>Trachinotus rhodopus</i>	CARANGIDAE	R
<i>Prionotus pictus</i>	TRIGLIDAE	RE	<i>Trachinotus stilbe</i>	CARANGIDAE	R
<i>Lepidonectes corallicola</i>	TRIPTERYGIIDAE	RE	<i>Trachurus murphyi</i>	CARANGIDAE	R
<i>Zanclus cornutus</i>	ZANCLIDAE	R	<i>Uraspis helvola</i>	CARANGIDAE	R

TABLE 6 (p. 1)

Fishes of the Galapagos Archipelago
deepwater demersal (non-pelagic) (126 spp.)

Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Anthias noeli</i>	ANTHIADIDAE	R	<i>Notorynchus cepedianus</i>	HEXANCHIDAE	R
<i>Hemanthias peruanus</i>	ANTHIADIDAE	V	<i>Howella pammelas</i>	HOWELLIDAE	R
<i>Pronotogrammus multifasciatus</i>	ANTHIADIDAE	R	<i>Bathypterois atricolor</i>	IPNOPIDAE	R
<i>Bathyraja abyssicola</i>	ARHYNCHOBATIDAE	R	<i>Bathypterois pectinatus</i>	IPNOPIDAE	R
<i>Bathyraja peruana</i>	ARHYNCHOBATIDAE	R	<i>Ipnops agassizii</i>	IPNOPIDAE	R
<i>Bathyraja richardsoni</i>	ARHYNCHOBATIDAE	R	<i>Decodon melasma</i>	LABRIDAE	R
<i>Bathyraja spinosissima</i>	ARHYNCHOBATIDAE	R	<i>Sagittalarva inornata</i>	LABRIDAE	R
<i>Aulopus chirichignoae</i>	AULOPIDAE	R	<i>Liopropoma longilepis</i>	LIOPROPOMATIDAE	R
<i>Monolene maculipinna</i>	BOTHIDAE	V	<i>Paraliparis darwini</i>	LIPARIDAE	RE
<i>Bellottia</i> sp.	BYTHITIDAE	R	<i>Paraliparis galapagosensis</i>	LIPARIDAE	RE
<i>Cataetyx rubirostris</i>	BYTHITIDAE	R	<i>Lophiodes spilurus</i>	LOPHIIDAE	R
<i>Cataetyx simus</i>	BYTHITIDAE	R	<i>Coelorinchus canus</i>	MACROURIDAE	R
<i>Diplacanthopoma jordani</i>	BYTHITIDAE	R	<i>Coryphaenoides anguliceps</i>	MACROURIDAE	R
<i>Lucifuga inopinata</i>	BYTHITIDAE	RE	<i>Coryphaenoides armatus</i>	MACROURIDAE	R
<i>Pseudonus acutus</i>	BYTHITIDAE	R	<i>Coryphaenoides boops</i>	MACROURIDAE	R
<i>Thermichthys hollisi</i>	BYTHITIDAE	RE	<i>Coryphaenoides bucephalus</i>	MACROURIDAE	R
<i>Centrophorus squamosus</i>	CENTROPHORIDAE	R	<i>Coryphaenoides bulbiceps</i>	MACROURIDAE	R
<i>Chaunacops coloratus</i>	CHAUNACIDAE	R	<i>Coryphaenoides delsolari</i>	MACROURIDAE	R
<i>Hydrolagus alphas</i>	CHIMAERIDAE	RE	<i>Coryphaenoides gypsochilus</i>	MACROURIDAE	RE
<i>Hydrolagus mccoskeri</i>	CHIMAERIDAE	RE	<i>Coryphaenoides myersi</i>	MACROURIDAE	RE
<i>Hydrolagus melanophasma</i>	CHIMAERIDAE	R	<i>Mataeocephalus tenuicauda</i>	MACROURIDAE	R
<i>Hydrolagus</i> n. sp.	CHIMAERIDAE	RE	<i>Nezumia convergens</i>	MACROURIDAE	R
<i>Chlopsis bicollaris</i>	CHLOPSIDAE	R	<i>Nezumia loricata</i>	MACROURIDAE	RE
<i>Chlorophthalmus mento</i>	CHLOROPHTHALMIDAE	R	<i>Nezumia parini</i>	MACROURIDAE	R
<i>Ariosoma gilberti</i>	CONGRIDAE	R	<i>Nezumia stelgidolepis</i>	MACROURIDAE	R
<i>Bathycongrus varidens</i>	CONGRIDAE	R	<i>Nezumia ventralis</i>	MACROURIDAE	RE
<i>Japonoconger proriger</i>	CONGRIDAE	R	<i>Antimora rostrata</i>	MORIDAE	R
<i>Paraconger californiensis</i>	CONGRIDAE	R	<i>Gadella filifer</i>	MORIDAE	R
<i>Paraconger similis</i>	CONGRIDAE	R	<i>Gadella thysthlon</i>	MORIDAE	RE
<i>Xenomystax atrarius</i>	CONGRIDAE	R	<i>Laemonema gracillipes</i>	MORIDAE	R
<i>Symphurus diabolicus</i>	CYNOGLOSSIDAE	R	<i>Physiculus nematopus</i>	MORIDAE	R
<i>Symphurus varius</i>	CYNOGLOSSIDAE	R	<i>Myroconger nigrodentatus</i>	MYROCONGRIDAE	R
<i>Taeniurops meyeri</i>	DASYATIDAE	R	<i>Eptatretus bobwisneri</i>	MYXINIDAE	RE
<i>Echinorhinus cookei</i>	ECHINORHINIDAE	R	<i>Eptatretus goslinei</i>	MYXINIDAE	RE
<i>Epigonus macrops</i>	EPIGONIDAE	R	<i>Eptatretus grouseri</i>	MYXINIDAE	RE
<i>Hyporthodus cifuentesi</i>	EPINEPHELIDAE	R	<i>Eptatretus mccoskeri</i>	MYXINIDAE	RE
<i>Centroscyllium nigrum</i>	ETMOPTERIDAE	R	<i>Myxine greggi</i>	MYXINIDAE	RE
<i>Gurgesiella furvescens</i>	GURGESIELLIDAE	R	<i>Myxine martinii</i>	MYXINIDAE	RE
<i>Halosaurus attenuatus</i>	HALOSAURIDAE	R	<i>Myxine phantasma</i>	MYXINIDAE	RE
<i>Hexanchus griseus</i>	HEXANCHIDAE	R	<i>Rubicundus lakeside</i>	MYXINIDAE	RE

TABLE 6 (p. 2)

Fishes of the Galapagos Archipelago
deepwater demersal (non-pelagic) (126 spp.)

Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Facciolella equatorialis</i>	NETTASTOMATIDAE	R	<i>Bellator farrago</i>	TRIGLIDAE	R
<i>Notacanthus spinosus</i>	NOTACANTHIDAE	R	<i>Peristedion crustosum</i>	TRIGLIDAE	R
<i>Dibranchius cracens</i>	OGCOEPHALIDAE	RE	<i>Lycodapus australis</i>	ZOARCIDAE	R
<i>Dibranchius discors</i>	OGCOEPHALIDAE	RE	<i>Melanostigma bathium</i>	ZOARCIDAE	R
<i>Dibranchius erinaceus</i>	OGCOEPHALIDAE	R	<i>Pachycara rimae</i>	ZOARCIDAE	RE
<i>Dibranchius hystrix</i>	OGCOEPHALIDAE	R	<i>Thermarces cerberus</i>	ZOARCIDAE	R
<i>Halieutopsis tumifrons</i>	OGCOEPHALIDAE	RE			
<i>Bathyonus caudalis</i>	OPHIDIIDAE	R			
<i>Dicrolene nigra</i>	OPHIDIIDAE	R			
<i>Eretmichthys pinnatus</i>	OPHIDIIDAE	R			
<i>Lamprogrammus niger</i>	OPHIDIIDAE	R			
<i>Monomitopus malispinosus</i>	OPHIDIIDAE	R			
<i>Monomitopus torvus</i>	OPHIDIIDAE	R			
<i>Porogadus promelas</i>	OPHIDIIDAE	R			
<i>Spectrunculus crassus</i>	OPHIDIIDAE	R			
<i>Apristurus kampae</i>	PENTANCHIDAE	R			
<i>Apristurus</i> n. sp.	PENTANCHIDAE	RE			
<i>Psychrolutes sio</i>	PSYCHROLUTIDAE	R			
<i>Rajella eisenhardti</i>	RAJIDAE	RE			
<i>Ectreposebastes imus</i>	SCORPAENIDAE	R			
<i>Idiastion hageyi</i>	SCORPAENIDAE	RE			
<i>Phenacoscorpius mccoskeri</i>	SCORPAENIDAE	RE			
<i>Pontinus clemensi</i>	SCORPAENIDAE	R			
<i>Pontinus furcirhinus</i>	SCORPAENIDAE	R			
<i>Pontinus sierra</i>	SCORPAENIDAE	R			
<i>Scorpaena cocosensis</i>	SCORPAENIDAE	R			
<i>Scorpaenodes rubrivinctus</i>	SCORPAENIDAE	R			
<i>Sebastolobus altivelis</i>	SCORPAENIDAE	R			
<i>Trachyscorpia osheri</i>	SCORPAENIDAE	R			
<i>Bythaelurus giddingsi</i>	SCYLORHINIDAE	RE			
<i>Galeus</i> n. sp.	SCYLORHINIDAE	RE			
<i>Serranus aequidens</i>	SERRANIDAE	R			
<i>Serranus stilbostigma</i>	SERRANIDAE	RE			
<i>Ilyophis arx</i>	SYNAPHOBRANCHIDAE	R			
<i>Ilyophis brunneus</i>	SYNAPHOBRANCHIDAE	R			
<i>Hoplostethus pacificus</i>	TRACHICHTHYIDAE	RE			
<i>Trachyrincus helolepis</i>	TRACHYRINCIDAE	R			
<i>Mustelus albipinnis</i>	TRIAKIDAE	R			
<i>Mustelus mento</i>	TRIAKIDAE	R			
<i>Triakis maculata</i>	TRIAKIDAE	R			

TABLE 7 (p. 1)

Fishes of the Galapagos Archipelago
offshore pelagics (101 spp.)

Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Aetobatus ocellatus</i>	AETOBATIDAE	R	<i>Hirundichthys speculiger</i>	EXOETIDAE	R
<i>Alopias pelagicus</i>	ALOPIIDAE	R	<i>Galeocerdo cuvier</i>	GALEOCERDONIDAE	R
<i>Ablennes hians</i>	BELONIDAE	R	<i>Gempylus serpens</i>	GEMPYLIDAE	R
<i>Brama dussumieri</i>	BRAMIDAE	R	<i>Lepidocybium flavobrunneum</i>	GEMPYLIDAE	R
<i>Brama japonica</i>	BRAMIDAE	V	<i>Nealotus tripes</i>	GEMPYLIDAE	R
<i>Taractes rubescens</i>	BRAMIDAE	R	<i>Ruvettus pretiosus</i>	GEMPYLIDAE	R
<i>Bregmaceros bathymaster</i>	BREGMACEROTIDAE	V	<i>Euleptorhamphus viridis</i>	HEMIRAMPHIDAE	R
<i>Naucrates ductor</i>	CARANGIDAE	R	<i>Oxyptorhamphus micropterus</i>	HEMIRAMPHIDAE	R
<i>Carcharhinus albimarginatus</i>	CARCHARHINIDAE	R	<i>Istiompax indica</i>	ISTIOPHORIDAE	R
<i>Carcharhinus altimus</i>	CARCHARHINIDAE	R	<i>Istiophorus platypterus</i>	ISTIOPHORIDAE	R
<i>Carcharhinus amblyrhynchus</i>	CARCHARHINIDAE	V	<i>Kajikia audax</i>	ISTIOPHORIDAE	R
<i>Carcharhinus falciformis</i>	CARCHARHINIDAE	R	<i>Makaira nigricans</i>	ISTIOPHORIDAE	R
<i>Carcharhinus galapagensis</i>	CARCHARHINIDAE	R	<i>Tetrapturus angustirostris</i>	ISTIOPHORIDAE	R
<i>Carcharhinus limbatus</i>	CARCHARHINIDAE	R	<i>Carcharodon carcharias</i>	LAMNIDAE	V
<i>Carcharhinus longimanus</i>	CARCHARHINIDAE	R	<i>Isurus oxyrinchus</i>	LAMNIDAE	R
<i>Nasolamia velox</i>	CARCHARHINIDAE	R	<i>Luvarus imperialis</i>	LUVARIDAE	R
<i>Prionace glauca</i>	CARCHARHINIDAE	R	<i>Mobula birostris</i>	MOBULIDAE	R
<i>Triaenodon obesus</i>	CARCHARHINIDAE	R	<i>Mobula mobular</i>	MOBULIDAE	R
<i>Paracaristius</i> sp.	CARISTIIDAE	R	<i>Mobula munkiana</i>	MOBULIDAE	R
<i>Serioloella violacea</i>	CENTROLOPHIDAE	R	<i>Mobula tarapacana</i>	MOBULIDAE	R
<i>Coryphaena equiselis</i>	CORYPHAENIDAE	R	<i>Mobula thurstoni</i>	MOBULIDAE	R
<i>Coryphaena hippurus</i>	CORYPHAENIDAE	R	<i>Masturus lanceolatus</i>	MOLIDAE	R
<i>Isistius brasiliensis</i>	DALATIIDAE	R	<i>Mola alexandrini</i>	MOLIDAE	R
<i>Pteroplatytrygon violacea</i>	DASYATIDAE	R	<i>Aetomylaeus asperrimus</i>	MYLIOBATIDAE	V
<i>Echeneis naucrates</i>	ECHENEIDAE	R	<i>Myliobatis peruviana</i>	MYLIOBATIDAE	R
<i>Phtheichthys lineatus</i>	ECHENEIDAE	R	<i>Cubiceps baxteri</i>	NOMEIDAE	R
<i>Remora albescens</i>	ECHENEIDAE	R	<i>Cubiceps pauciradiatus</i>	NOMEIDAE	R
<i>Remora brachyptera</i>	ECHENEIDAE	R	<i>Nomeus gronovii</i>	NOMEIDAE	R
<i>Remora osteochir</i>	ECHENEIDAE	R	<i>Psenes arafurensis</i>	NOMEIDAE	R
<i>Remora remora</i>	ECHENEIDAE	R	<i>Psenes cyanophrys</i>	NOMEIDAE	R
<i>Cheilopogon atrisignis</i>	EXOETIDAE	R	<i>Psenes pellucidus</i>	NOMEIDAE	R
<i>Cheilopogon dorsomaculata</i>	EXOETIDAE	R	<i>Psenes sio</i>	NOMEIDAE	R
<i>Cheilopogon furcatus</i>	EXOETIDAE	R	<i>Odontaspis ferox</i>	ODONTASPIDIDAE	R
<i>Cheilopogon spilonotopterus</i>	EXOETIDAE	R	<i>Lactoria diaphana</i>	OSTRACIIDAE	V
<i>Cheilopogon xenopterus</i>	EXOETIDAE	R	<i>Regalecus russellii</i>	REGALECIDAE	R
<i>Cypselurus callopterus</i>	EXOETIDAE	R	<i>Rhincodon typus</i>	RHINCODONTIDAE	R
<i>Exocoetus monocirrhus</i>	EXOETIDAE	R	<i>Rhinoptera steindachneri</i>	RHINOPTERIDAE	R
<i>Exocoetus volitans</i>	EXOETIDAE	R	<i>Cololabis adoceta</i>	SCOMBERESOCIDAE	R
<i>Fodiator rostratus</i>	EXOETIDAE	R	<i>Scomberesox scombroides</i>	SCOMBERESOCIDAE	R
<i>Hirundichthys marginatus</i>	EXOETIDAE	R	<i>Acanthocybium solandri</i>	SCOMBRIDAE	R

TABLE 7 (p. 2)

Fishes of the Galapagos Archipelago
offshore pelagics (101 spp.)

Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Auxis rochei</i>	SCOMBRIDAE	R
<i>Auxis thazard</i>	SCOMBRIDAE	R
<i>Euthynnus lineatus</i>	SCOMBRIDAE	R
<i>Katsuwonus pelamis</i>	SCOMBRIDAE	R
<i>Sarda orientalis</i>	SCOMBRIDAE	R
<i>Scomber japonicus</i>	SCOMBRIDAE	R
<i>Scomberomorus sierra</i>	SCOMBRIDAE	R
<i>Thunnus albacares</i>	SCOMBRIDAE	R
<i>Thunnus obesus</i>	SCOMBRIDAE	R
<i>Sphyrna lewini</i>	SPHYRNIDAE	R
<i>Sphyrna zygaena</i>	SPHYRNIDAE	R
<i>Peprilus medius</i>	STROMATEIDAE	R
<i>Tetragonurus atlanticus</i>	TETRAGONURIDAE	R
<i>Lagocephalus lagocephalus</i>	TETRAODONTIDAE	R
<i>Desmodema polystictum</i>	TRACHIPTERIDAE	R
<i>Zu cristatus</i>	TRACHIPTERIDAE	R
<i>Aphanopus capricornis</i>	TRICHIURIDAE	R
<i>Benthodesmus tenuis</i>	TRICHIURIDAE	R
<i>Lepidopus manis</i>	TRICHIURIDAE	R
<i>Trichiurus nitens</i>	TRICHIURIDAE	R
<i>Xiphias gladius</i>	XIPHIIDAE	R

TABLE 8 (p. 1)

Fishes of the Galapagos Archipelago
mesopelagic fishes (136 spp.)

Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Bathytroctes macrolepis</i>	ALEPOCEPHALIDAE	R	<i>Bolinichthys longipes</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R
<i>Einara macrolepis</i>	ALEPOCEPHALIDAE	R	<i>Centrobranchus andreae</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R
<i>Narcetes erimelas</i>	ALEPOCEPHALIDAE	R	<i>Centrobranchus nigroocellatus</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R
<i>Photostylus pycnopterus</i>	ALEPOCEPHALIDAE	R	<i>Dasyscopelus asper</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R
<i>Alopias superciliosus</i>	ALOPIIDAE	R	<i>Diaphus fulgens</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R
<i>Anoplogaster cornuta</i>	ANOLOGASTRIDAE	R	<i>Diaphus mollis</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R
<i>Argentina alicae</i>	ARGENTINIDAE	R	<i>Diaphus pacificus</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R
<i>Guentherus altivela</i>	ATELEPODIDAE	R	<i>Diaphus parri</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R
<i>Bathylagoides nigrigenys</i>	BATHYLAGIDAE	R	<i>Diaphus rafinesquii</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R
<i>Bathylagus wesethi</i>	BATHYLAGIDAE	R	<i>Diaphus termophilus</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R
<i>Leuroglossus stilbius</i>	BATHYLAGIDAE	R	<i>Diaphus theta</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R
<i>Cryptopsaras couesii</i>	CERATIIDAE	R	<i>Diogenichthys laternatus</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R
<i>Cetomimus gillii</i>	CETOMIMIDAE	R	<i>Gonichthys tenuiculus</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R
<i>Chiasmodon niger</i>	CHIASMODONTIDAE	R	<i>Gonichthys venetus</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R
<i>Chiasmodon subniger</i>	CHIASMODONTIDAE	R	<i>Hygophum reinhardtii</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R
<i>Evermannella ahlstromi</i>	EVERMANNELLIDAE	R	<i>Lampadena luminosa</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R
<i>Gigantactis vanhoeffeni</i>	GIGANTACTINIDAE	R	<i>Lampanyctus crypticus</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R
<i>Cyclothone acclinidens</i>	GONOSTOMATIDAE	R	<i>Lampanyctus hubbsi</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R
<i>Cyclothone alba</i>	GONOSTOMATIDAE	R	<i>Lampanyctus idostigma</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R
<i>Cyclothone atraria</i>	GONOSTOMATIDAE	R	<i>Lampanyctus macropterus</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R
<i>Cyclothone braueri</i>	GONOSTOMATIDAE	R	<i>Lampanyctus nobilis</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R
<i>Cyclothone microdon</i>	GONOSTOMATIDAE	R	<i>Lampanyctus omostigma</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R
<i>Cyclothone obscura</i>	GONOSTOMATIDAE	R	<i>Lampanyctus parvicauda</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R
<i>Cyclothone pallida</i>	GONOSTOMATIDAE	R	<i>Lampanyctus ritteri</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R
<i>Cyclothone pseudopallida</i>	GONOSTOMATIDAE	R	<i>Lampanyctus tenuiformis</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R
<i>Cyclothone signata</i>	GONOSTOMATIDAE	R	<i>Loweina rara</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R
<i>Diplophos proximus</i>	GONOSTOMATIDAE	R	<i>Myctophum brachygnathum</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R
<i>Sigmops elongatus</i>	GONOSTOMATIDAE	R	<i>Myctophum affine</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R
<i>Borophryne apogon</i>	LINOPHRYNIDAE	R	<i>Myctophum aurolaternatum</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R
<i>Melamphaes laeviceps</i>	MELAMPHAIDAE	R	<i>Myctophum nitidulum</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R
<i>Melamphaes spinifer</i>	MELAMPHAIDAE	R	<i>Notolychnus valdiviae</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R
<i>Poromitra cf. crassiceps</i>	MELAMPHAIDAE	R	<i>Notoscopelus elongatus</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R
<i>Poromitra frontosa</i>	MELAMPHAIDAE	R	<i>Notoscopelus resplendens</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R
<i>Poromitra jucunda</i>	MELAMPHAIDAE	R	<i>Protomyctophum sp.</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R
<i>Poromitra nigrofulva</i>	MELAMPHAIDAE	R	<i>Symbolophorus evermanni</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R
<i>Poromitra oscitans</i>	MELAMPHAIDAE	R	<i>Symbolophorus reversus</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R
<i>Scopeloberyx opisthopterus</i>	MELAMPHAIDAE	R	<i>Triphoturus mexicanus</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R
<i>Scopeloberyx robustus</i>	MELAMPHAIDAE	R	<i>Triphoturus nigricans</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R
<i>Scopelogadus bispinosus</i>	MELAMPHAIDAE	R	<i>Triphoturus oculus</i>	MYCTOPHIDAE	R
<i>Melanocetus murrayi</i>	MELANOCETIDAE	R	<i>Avocettina infans</i>	NEMICHTHYIDAE	R

TABLE 8 (p. 2)

Fishes of the Galapagos Archipelago
mesopelagic fishes (136 spp.)

Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic	Species	Family	Resident Vagrant Endemic
<i>Nemichthys scolopaceus</i>	NEMICHTHYIDAE	R	<i>Astronesthes gibbsi</i>	STOMIIDAE	R
<i>Scopelogys tristis</i>	NEOSCOPELIDAE	R	<i>Astronesthes indica</i>	STOMIIDAE	R
<i>Scopelosaurus harryi</i>	NOTOSUDIDAE	R	<i>Astronesthes lampara</i>	STOMIIDAE	R
<i>Scopelosaurus hubbsi</i>	NOTOSUDIDAE	R	<i>Bathophilus filifer</i>	STOMIIDAE	R
<i>Chaenophryne draco</i>	ONEIRODIDAE	R	<i>Borostomias elucens</i>	STOMIIDAE	R
<i>Dolopichthys allector</i>	ONEIRODIDAE	R	<i>Borostomias panamensis</i>	STOMIIDAE	R
<i>Microlophichthys microlophus</i>	ONEIRODIDAE	R	<i>Chauliodus barbatus</i>	STOMIIDAE	R
<i>Pentherichthys atratus</i>	ONEIRODIDAE	R	<i>Chauliodus sloani</i>	STOMIIDAE	R
<i>Bathylychnops</i> sp.	OPISTHOPROCTIDAE	R	<i>Idiacanthus antrostomus</i>	STOMIIDAE	R
<i>Dolichopteryx pseudolongipes</i>	OPISTHOPROCTIDAE	R	<i>Malacosteus niger</i>	STOMIIDAE	R
<i>Lestidiops pacificus</i>	PARALEPIDIDAE	R	<i>Photonectes margarita</i>	STOMIIDAE	R
<i>Lestidium bigelowi</i>	PARALEPIDIDAE	R	<i>Stomias atriventer</i>	STOMIIDAE	R
<i>Stemonosudis macrura</i>	PARALEPIDIDAE	R	<i>Stomias colubrinus</i>	STOMIIDAE	R
<i>Ichthyococcus irregularis</i>	PHOSICHTHYIDAE	R	<i>Stomias danae</i>	STOMIIDAE	R
<i>Vinciguerria lucetius</i>	PHOSICHTHYIDAE	R	<i>Thysanactis dentex</i>	STOMIIDAE	R
<i>Vinciguerria nimbaria</i>	PHOSICHTHYIDAE	R	<i>Stylephorus chordatus</i>	STYLEPHORIDAE	R
<i>Vinciguerria poweriae</i>	PHOSICHTHYIDAE	R			
<i>Yarella argenteola</i>	PHOSICHTHYIDAE	R			
<i>Holtbyrnia latifrons</i>	PLATYTROCTIDAE	R			
<i>Maulisia isaacsi</i>	PLATYTROCTIDAE	R			
<i>Platytrectes apus</i>	PLATYTROCTIDAE	R			
<i>Sagamichthys abei</i>	PLATYTROCTIDAE	R			
<i>Rondeletia loricata</i>	RONDELETIIDAE	R			
<i>Rosenblattichthys volucris</i>	SCOPELARCHIDAE	R			
<i>Scopelarchoides nicholsi</i>	SCOPELARCHIDAE	R			
<i>Scopelarchus guentheri</i>	SCOPELARCHIDAE	R			
<i>Serrivomer sector</i>	SERRIVOMERIDAE	R			
<i>Argyropelecus aculeatus</i>	STERNOPTYCHIDAE	R			
<i>Argyropelecus affinis</i>	STERNOPTYCHIDAE	R			
<i>Argyropelecus lychnus</i>	STERNOPTYCHIDAE	R			
<i>Argyropelecus olfersii</i>	STERNOPTYCHIDAE	R			
<i>Argyropelecus sladeni</i>	STERNOPTYCHIDAE	R			
<i>Danaphos oculatus</i>	STERNOPTYCHIDAE	R			
<i>Maurolicus australis</i>	STERNOPTYCHIDAE	R			
<i>Sternoptyx diaphana</i>	STERNOPTYCHIDAE	R			
<i>Sternoptyx obscura</i>	STERNOPTYCHIDAE	R			
<i>Sternoptyx pseudobscura</i>	STERNOPTYCHIDAE	R			
<i>Valencienellus tripunctulatus</i>	STERNOPTYCHIDAE	R			
<i>Astronesthes cyanea</i>	STOMIIDAE	R			
<i>Astronesthes galapagensis</i>	STOMIIDAE	R			